

AI Corner 🤖

Designing a Module on the Responsible Use of Generative AI for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) Instruction

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Abstract

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Title AI Corner Designing a Module on the Responsible Use of Generative AI for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) Instruction		
<p>This report outlines the <i>AI Corner</i> project, developed as part of the DigiErko Professional Specialization Studies throughout the academic year of 2024 and completed in early 2025. The project was conducted at the joint Language Centre of LAB University of Applied Sciences and LUT University, specifically in the context of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction.</p> <p>The project's aim was to design and pilot a 1-ECTS module to introduce AI basics, AI terminology, AI ethics and risks, and the use of generative AI in the writing process in English. The module was designed so that it could be integrated as a 1-ECTS component into compulsory ESP-informed courses at the LAB/LUT Language Centre or offered as a standalone 1-ECTS asynchronous online course.</p> <p>The design process drew on educational design research and learning experience design. The project was also guided by concepts of AI Literacy and the TPACK framework.</p> <p>The project involved empirical research in the form of two online surveys. The first examined students' use of and opinions on AI tools. These results informed the design of the pilot version of <i>AI Corner</i>. The second survey collected students' exit feedback on the pilot version to update and develop the module further where needed.</p> <p>The result of the project is the <i>AI Corner</i> module, renamed <i>English and AI: Terminology, Ethics and Writing</i>, which will be added to the Language Centre ESP course catalog from autumn 2025.</p>		
Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, AI Literacy, Educational Design Research, English for Specific Purposes, Generative AI, Higher Education, Learning Experience Design, Module Design, Responsible use of AI, TPACK		

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Introduction

Technologies aren't neutral. They are a philosophy and an ideology. –Zadie Smith

We shape our tools, and thereafter our tools shape us. –John Culkin

But lo! men have become the tools of their tools. –Henry David Thoreau

The use of artificial intelligence tools has proliferated in recent years, particularly since OpenAI, a San Francisco-based AI company, released ChatGPT, a generative AI (GenAI) chatbot, to the public in November 2022. ChatGPT reached a hundred million users within only two months after its launch. To put this in perspective, it took social media platforms and audio streaming services such as TikTok 9 months, Instagram 30 months, and Spotify 55 months to reach that same number, the pace was unparalleled. (Dobrin 2023, 17–18) Given the integration of ChatGPT-like GenAI tools into software, operating systems, and smartphones, it's far from hyperbole to say that these tools will soon become enmeshed in most professionals' workflows.

GenAI tools—often powered by Large Language Models or Large Multimodal Models (LLMs/LMMs)—are a subset of artificial intelligence tools and encompass a wide range of systems capable of generating text, images, audio, video, and code in response to their users' prompts written or spoken in natural language. With intuitive chat-like user interfaces, these systems have been designed to simulate human-like conversation so well that the learning curve for using them is virtually nonexistent. Some have dubbed Large Models (e.g., LLMs/LMMs) “a new kind of cultural and social technology, allowing humans to take advantage of information other humans have accumulated” and, moreover, likened them to past social technologies such as writing and print, even representative democracy (Farrell et al. 2025, 1153).

GenAI's transformative functionality becomes immediately evident in writing contexts. In writing instruction, similar to traditional assistive writing tools (e.g., Grammarly, Microsoft Editor, and others), also known as “constructive artificial intelligence” (Paiz, Toncelli & Kostka 2025), GenAIs can provide feedback on clarity, cohesion, grammar, spelling, and punctuation. GenAIs are even more capable in that they can be prompted to provide complete editorial feedback, paraphrase and summarize text, write cohesive paragraphs, and generate complete essays, articles, reports, and other texts. Capabilities like these challenge higher education, where learning assessment has traditionally relied heavily on written work (see e.g., Medina 2024, vii).

One specific area of pedagogy that could help meet the challenge is professional communication and writing instruction in the context of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) teaching. Since ESP has traditionally been defined as focused on the needs of learners who will be using English at work or for their studies (Basturkmen 2010, 3; see also Dudley-Evans & St. John 1998, 3–5), I propose tentatively that teaching responsible use of GenAI tools could align well with ESP's needs-based approach.

The use of GenAI tools has already attracted attention in the contexts of English language teaching, writing instruction, and business communication research. The potential impact and use of spellcheck and editing tools, machine translation, and similar technologies had already been noticed before the widespread adoption of GenAIs. For instance, in his pre-ChatGPT-era article on AI writing assistance, Goodwin-Jones (2022, 5) observes that “it may be time to learn to live with the reality of students’ access to advanced writing assistance and find ways to provide appropriate guidance.” Based on a survey of 343 business communication instructors, Cardon et al.’s slightly later-published study seems to confirm Goodwin-Jones’s observation:

“Among the most salient observations from instructors is that they needed to change their teaching to integrate AI-related content into their courses. Instructors often reasoned that these tools should be addressed because they will be widely used in the workplace and that students are using them outside the classroom.” (Cardon et al. 2023, 255)

In the context of language teaching, Kohnke (2023) has found that chatbots may help engage second or foreign language learners, while Kohnke, Moorhouse and Zou (2023) maintain that “ChatGPT supports language learning by simulating authentic interactions.” Mahapatra (2024), moreover, notes that ChatGPT can serve as a formative feedback tool during the writing process and can have positive impacts on English as a second language learners’ academic writing skills. In their study of Thai and Vietnamese EFL learners’ perceptions of using ChatGPT for second language writing, Mediano et al. (2024) conclude that “the respondents of this study perceived ChatGPT positively. They find it helpful in enhancing their writing skill and subskills [...]” The authors also caution that proper resources, support, and guidance are needed. And, finally, Paiz, Toncelli and Kostka (2025) emphasize that English language teachers are at a juncture, weighing GenAI’s potential benefits and risks for English language teaching.

Amid the growing enthusiasm, even hype, surrounding GenAI’s potential, critical voices and concerns must also be considered. Critical AI, a journal based at Rutgers University, warns on its AI Hype Wall of Shame page against “pervasive AI “hype” that currently misleads the public about “artificial intelligence” (AI) in its various dimensions.” Concerns like this are particularly relevant for us educators, who should critically evaluate claims about GenAI’s affordances and

guard against what Narayanan and Kapoor (2024, 2) describe as AI snake oil: “AI that does not and cannot work as advertised.”¹ Some have even characterized the term artificial intelligence itself as a marketing construct, an “empty signifier” (Popenci 2023; Lindgren 2023, according to Rudolph et al. 2025, 8).

To investigate how ESP pedagogy could incorporate GenAI tools, I designed and worked on an educational design research capstone project aimed at introducing the basics of responsible GenAI use to ESP learners at the Language Centre of LAB University of Applied Sciences (LAB) and LUT University (LUT).

Conducted during the academic year of 2024 and completed in early spring 2025, my project was part of the DigiErko postgraduate continuing education studies in the Faculty of Educational Sciences, University of Helsinki. It was supervised by University Lecturer Tiina Korhonen, PhD, and Project Manager Sorella Karme, MA, from the University of Helsinki. Team Manager Ritva Kosonen, PhLic, from the Language Centre acted as a project mentor; the research permit was granted by the Director of the Language Centre, Pasi Puranen. Several of my colleagues, Ella Hujala, Vesa Koskela, Tessa Laba, Anneli Rinnevali, and Hanna Vihava, helped collect data or acted as sparring partners.

My project sits at the intersection of digital pedagogy, AI literacy, and English language and communication teaching. It involved designing and piloting an online module, *AI Corner*², which focuses on the basics of responsible GenAI use in English. *AI Corner* can be integrated as a self-study component within certain ESP courses at the Language Centre, or it can be offered as a standalone 1 ECTS asynchronous online course.

To create *AI Corner*, I gathered data on students’ use, understanding of, and opinions on AI tools. This data was collected through two questionnaires: I administered the first one to students enrolled in various ESP courses during the spring semester of 2024, and the second one to students who participated in the pilot run of *AI Corner* in the autumn semester of 2024.

For transparency, I’d briefly like to describe the use of GenAI tools in writing this report. I’ve used Claude 3.5 Sonnet (Anthropic), Claude 3.7 Sonnet (Anthropic), GPT-4o (OpenAI),

¹ In the context of academic integrity, writing, and English language teaching, AI detectors might be one example of AI snake oil being sold to educators. An ongoing debate questions whether AI detectors can deliver on their promises, with one widely cited study claiming that these detectors might be biased against non-native English learners (Liang et al. 2023). Education technology companies Originality.ai and Turnitin have, however, responded by publishing their own research to counter these findings (e.g., Adamson 2023; Gillham 2024). A study by Jiang et al. (2024) also found no evidence of such bias against non-native English learners.

² I want to thank my colleague, Senior Lecturer Olesia Kullberg, for coining the name, *AI Corner*.

OpenAI o3-mini high (OpenAI), and Gemini 2.0 Flash (Google) hosted on the Poe.com platform. When using these AIs, I've prompted them, for example, as follows:

Role: Act as an editor. **Focus area:** Provide editorial feedback on cohesion, logic, and structure. Proofread for grammar, spelling, and punctuation. Additionally, make sure that key terms and expressions are used consistently. **Boundaries:** Do not rewrite. Respect my original authorial voice and only provide feedback on objective mistakes. **Context:** I am writing an academic report about a postgraduate project titled *AI Corner*. **Feedback format:** Provide your feedback in bullets.

In addition to editorial assistance, I used Claude 3.7 Sonnet (Anthropic) and o3-mini high (OpenAI) on Poe.com to interact with the results of my two questionnaires by uploading parts of the results reports to AIs (no personal information about respondents was gathered in the questionnaires). This helped me examine and draw some conclusions based on the data. Claude 3.7 Sonnet and o3-mini high are AI models that have what are known as reasoning capabilities; they pause and “think” before they generate their answers, which is believed to improve the output (Mollick 2025). I generated the timeline visualizations in Chapter 3.3 and the CES table (Table 13) in Chapter 4.3 by prompting Claude 3.7 Sonnet on Poe.com. To finalize the report contents, I prompted Claude 3.7 Sonnet on Poe.com to review my report draft and generate recommendations. I curated the list and added it Chapter 5.1. Finally, I prompted Claude 3.7 Sonnet to check my finalized report and compare all in-text citations against the references list and to check for numbering issues in figures, images, and tables throughout the document. Despite using GenAI tools for some assistance as I've described here, all core thinking and writing remains my own; except for the recommendations, I didn't use AI tools to generate original ideas or text for this report.

I'm aware that anthropomorphizing GenAI tools—for instance, instructing a GenAI tool to adopt human-like roles—can be questioned, even considered a risk. While role-prompting is a commonly discussed technique that could potentially help elicit better responses from GenAI tools (see e.g., Mollick & Mollick 2023; Schulhoff 2024), there's uncertainty as to how much, if at all, this improves GenAI performance (see e.g., Zheng et al. 2024).

I've structured the report as follows. It's divided into five main chapters and ends with a reflection and conclusion: 1. AI Literacy and TPACK, 2. Educational Design Research and Learning Experience Design, 3. AI Corner: Project Description, 4. AI Corner: Designing and Piloting the Module, and 5. Recommendations, Dissemination and Use. Following these, the Reflection and Conclusion section ends the report.

To contextualize my project, I begin by discussing AI literacy and the TPACK framework in Chapter 1. In Chapter 2, I move on to introduce the concepts of educational design research and learning experience design as background. Then, in Chapter 3, I proceed to describe the project needs assessment, LAB and LUT students' use of AI tools and opinions on them, as well as the project timeline and target groups. In Chapter 4, I focus on explaining how I designed and piloted the *AI Corner* module, and in Chapter 5 I present a list of recommendations, outline the dissemination of the project, and discuss possible future uses of *AI Corner*. In the concluding chapter, I reflect on and summarize my professional development process throughout the project.

1 AI Literacy and TPACK

1.1 AI Literacy Frameworks

The concept of AI literacy helps contextualize the *AI Corner* project and connects it to a broader academic framework. Recent academic and popular discussions about higher education pedagogy have recognized the urgent need for AI literacy, even the need for teacher training to include AI literacy (e.g., Cardon et al. 2023; O’Dea & O’Dea 2023; Chan & Colloton 2024, 24; Jensen 2024; Prilop et al. 2024; Werner 2024). I also contributed modestly to all this by publishing a short blog post, *Teaching critical AI literacy is a must* (Guedra 2024a), on LAB Focus, a blog platform of LAB University of Applied Sciences.

AI literacy has a broad scope. It’s not only about technological understanding but also about the ethics and socio-cultural impacts of AI, as well as metacognition. In the book *Generative AI in Higher Education*, Chan and Colloton (2024, 24) define AI literacy as “knowing how AI works and how to use it wisely and ethically. It is not only about being tech-savvy; it is also about understanding AI’s impact, making smart choices, and being aware of the ethical issues that it raises.” While they note that agreement on the definition of AI literacy is still lacking, Chan and Colloton (2024, 32–33) propose a foundational AI Literacy Framework with five components: 1) Understanding AI Concepts, 2) Awareness of AI Applications, 3) AI Affectiveness for Human Emotions, 4) AI Safety and Security, and 5) Responsible AI Usage (Figure 1).

Figure 1. AI Literacy Framework (based on Chan & Colloton 2024, 32–33)

Let’s examine the five components. The first one, Understanding AI Concepts (1), is about learning AI concepts, such as machine learning, neural networks, and data processing. Knowing concepts like these helps individuals use AI technologies better as they familiarize themselves with what AI systems are capable of. The second component, Awareness of AI Applications (2), focuses on becoming aware of AI’s presence, for instance, in fields such as

healthcare, education, finance, and entertainment. The third component, AI Affectiveness for Human Emotions (3), concerns AI's ability to respond to and interact with human emotions; it's about AI simulating emotional intelligence and adapting to its user's emotional cues. The fourth component, AI Safety and Security (4), addresses AI risks, such as privacy breaches and biases. Being aware of AI safety and security helps individuals protect themselves against AI risks and make better choices when interacting with AI systems. Finally, the fifth component of Chan and Colloton's AI Literacy framework, Responsible AI Usage (5), deals with AI ethics. The rationale is that individuals who know how to use AI systems responsibly don't overly rely on or misuse them but advocate their informed use. (Chan & Colloton 2024, 32–33)

Context determines the expected level of understanding of the five components. For the average individual, a general understanding suffices. In contrast, a professional who uses AI-powered systems at work needs a deeper understanding of all, or at least some, of the five components; this is domain-specific AI literacy. The deepest understanding, even mastery, across all five components is, then, required from experts who develop AI systems. (Chan & Colloton 2024, 33–35)

While Chan and Colloton's AI Literacy Framework offers a widely applicable approach for higher education, Paiz, Toncelli and Kostka (2025) introduce a narrower Critical AI Literacy Framework designed specifically with English language teaching in mind. They define the concept of critical AI literacy as “[t]he ability to understand, evaluate, and ethically use artificial intelligence, recognizing its capabilities, limitations, and societal impacts, particularly in the context of education and daily life.” Similar to Chan and Colloton's framework, the Critical AI Literacy Framework has five components: 1) Understanding the Pedagogical Impacts of AI Systems, 2) Understanding the Fundamentals of AI Systems, 3) Knowledge of the Limits and Capabilities of AI Systems, 4) Habits of Mind Necessary to Use AI Systems and Evaluate the Output of AI Systems, and 5) Knowledge of AI Ethics and Algorithmic Fairness (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Critical AI Literacy Framework (based on Paiz, Toncelli & Kostka 2025)

Let's briefly look at each component of Paiz, Toncelli and Kostka's framework. The first, Understanding the Pedagogical Impacts of AI Systems (1), is about GenAI's pedagogical potential as it can be leveraged to provide individualized learning experiences. GenAI tools can also help automate administrative tasks and potentially help learners become lifelong learners. The second component, Understanding the Fundamentals of AI Systems (2), as the authors explain, doesn't have to do with deep technical understanding but more with understanding "applicable metaphors for AI." It's about understanding that GenAI systems are often trained on data by using various machine learning techniques and about knowing some of the related terminology. The third component, Knowledge of the Limits and Capabilities of AI Systems (3), is about recognizing when a GenAI tool might and when it might not enhance expertise and meet one's needs. The fourth component, Habits of Mind Necessary to Use AI Systems and Evaluate the Output of AI Systems (4), focuses on how individuals employ their skills and knowledge to interact with GenAI-generated content and how they use GenAI tools. It's about flexibility and curiosity to test new tools, about exercising critical thinking and reflection, as well as problem solving. And, finally, it's about acquiring the skills needed to identify AI-generated outputs and mis- and disinformation. The fifth and final component of the framework, Knowledge of AI Ethics and Algorithmic Fairness (5), deals with fair and transparent uses of AI, as well as AI's societal impact and algorithmic bias, resulting from real societal biases. (Paiz, Toncelli & Kostka 2025)

The importance of AI literacy underlies the *AI Corner* project. As I've outlined in Table 1, the three learning outcomes I've designed for the *AI Corner* module correspond to several of the components included in Chan and Colloton's AI Literacy Framework and Paiz et al.'s Critical AI Literacy Framework.

Table 1. AI Corner learning outcomes compared with two AI literacy frameworks

AI Corner Learning Outcomes	AI Literacy Framework	Critical AI Literacy Framework
You can define and use key terms of AI in English.	(1) Understanding AI Concepts.	(2) Understanding the fundamentals of AI systems
You can identify AI risks and key points of AI ethics in English.	(4) Safety and AI Security. (5) Responsible AI Usage.	(3) Knowledge of the Limits and Capabilities of AI Systems (4) Habits of Mind Necessary to Use AI Systems and Evaluate the Output of AI Systems (5) Knowledge of AI Ethics and Algorithmic Fairness
You can use AI tools responsibly for professional writing in English.	(5) Responsible AI Usage.	(4) Habits of Mind Necessary to Use AI Systems and Evaluate the Output of AI Systems (5) Knowledge of AI Ethics and Algorithmic Fairness

1.2 TPACK Framework

For some educators, incorporating GenAI tools, much less teaching AI literacy, into their teaching practice can feel daunting, even cause resistance at first. Indeed, educators' emotions have been described ranging anywhere from "curiosity and trepidation" to "excitement, fear [and] anxiety [...]" (Kostka & Toncelli 2023; Paiz, Toncelli & Kostka 2025). Such a range of emotional responses highlights educators' need to carefully reflect on GenAI's impact.

Studies have revealed reasons why some might feel hesitant. Cardon et al. (2023, 267), for instance, surveyed 343 business communication instructors on AI-assisted writing and developing AI literacy. While many accepted the need to integrate AI into coursework, some were more hesitant and gave reasons for resistance. They felt that they lacked the ability to adapt, or the time needed to update their knowledge. Some respondents also noted only seeing problems without solutions, while some emphasized more training will be needed to better understand AI tools.

Considering the list of questions in Reeves and Sylvia's article on GenAI and technical communication, it's no surprise some educators feel intimidated:

"What are appropriate and inappropriate uses of GAI in student writing, in teaching, and in professional communication? How can our students use GAI tools to master writing skills without being mastered by the tools? How much can we trust these tools to produce valid and truthful results? As GAI tools are fed more data and as our prompting strategies improve, will they change our conceptions of the nature of writing and authorship? What if we cannot distinguish human from GAI written texts? And what if we forget how to write, just as many of us have forgotten how to spell due to spellchecker bots?" (Reeves & Sylvia 2024, 440)

Additionally, Paiz, Toncelli and Kostka (2025) point out that, because of dense technical descriptions, an array of new AI applications and platforms, and expanding conversations on AI, a sense of feeling lost may arise. While many educators feel somewhat lost and continue to pose questions like the ones I've quoted above, there are those who have already begun to actively resist and problematize any overly simplified ideas about integrating GenAI into writing instruction. For instance, a group of writing studies scholars has launched an online initiative, *Refusing Generative AI in Writing Studies*, to critically debate GenAI's impact specifically on writing studies (see e.g., Sano-Franchini, McIntyre & Fernandes 2024). Given all this, incorporating GenAI tool usage into writing and communication instruction clearly remains debated and a challenge.

One traditional framework to help us consider, possibly even plan and scaffold, how to integrate technology into our pedagogy is Mishra and Koehler's (2006) TPACK framework, which includes three key domains: technological knowledge (TK), content knowledge (CK), and pedagogical knowledge (PK).

The TPACK framework is canonically presented as a Venn diagram, where the three domains overlap and interact. At their intersection is TPACK: technological pedagogical content knowledge. The revised version of the diagram also surrounds the three domains with an outer circle of contextual knowledge (XK). This constitutes the educator's knowledge of, for instance, the specific institution and its policies and culture, the available technologies, educational legislation, and so on (Mishra 2019, 76). Figure 3 shows the revised TPACK framework diagram.

Figure 3. Revised TPACK framework (Tpack.org 2012)

Reflecting on and applying the TPACK framework could help alleviate uncertainties concerning the adoption of GenAI tools. For instance, in the context of technical communication, which Reeves and Sylvia (2024) discuss, technical writing instructors likely possess practical experience and content knowledge (CK) of the linguistic registers, writing genres, processes, practices, and requirements of professional writing. They also have experience in teaching (PK), so they know how to teach the expected content. Most technical writing instructors likely also have at least some—perhaps even in-depth—technological knowledge (TK) of specialized

documentation tools, word processing software, spellcheckers, and integrated writing assistants, possibly even AI-powered writing assistants.

Additionally, the pedagogical knowledge (PK) component is evident in what Paiz, Toncelli and Kostka (2025) note about instructor expertise. Writing at the intersection of English language teaching (ELT) and AI-enhanced instruction, they emphasize that teachers have specific pedagogical expertise and know their students. No matter how much AI may have disrupted ELT, they point out, “good pedagogy is still good pedagogy.” As teachers, we decide when AI might best fit our “broader educational mission.” When it comes to language teachers specifically, Kohnke, Moorhouse and Zou (2023) have summarized the types of digital competence needed to use ChatGPT, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Digital competence to use ChatGPT (based on Kohnke, Moorhouse & Zou 2023)

Technological proficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be aware of the features of ChatGPT • Understand how ChatGPT works • Construct effective prompts and interact with ChatGPT • Troubleshoot challenges using ChatGPT in the classroom • Stay up-to-date with changes to ChatGPT
Pedagogical compatibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think about and plan ways to use ChatGPT to enhance or transform language teaching and learning tasks • Implement tasks that use ChatGPT • Guide learners to use ChatGPT for self-directed learning
Social awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a critical awareness of the drawbacks of ChatGPT and consider them when planning and implementing tasks • Inform learners of the risks, ethical issues, and drawbacks of ChatGPT

The digital competence outlined in Table 2 provides a foundation for language teachers to understand what’s needed for successful GenAI integration. When mapped to the TPACK framework, technological proficiency in Table 2 corresponds to TPACK’s technological knowledge (TK), while pedagogical compatibility aligns with TPACK’s pedagogical knowledge (PK). The social awareness component, however, falls slightly outside TPACK’s scope, although it could perhaps be considered part of pedagogical knowledge (PK).

The release of powerful technological innovations challenges higher education and its teaching practices. When confronted with a new technological innovation, such as ChatGPT-like GenAI tools now, those educators who have in-depth content (CK) and pedagogical knowledge (PK), as well as contextual knowledge (XK), can leverage this experience to their benefit in times of technological change. This can enable educators not only to adapt but critically reflect on and assess the risks and affordances of a given technological innovation in their field. But, where

needed, educators must be provided with opportunities for professional development and upskilling, as well as time to adapt and acquire the knowledge needed to teach effective and responsible use of new technologies, such as GenAI tools.

2 Educational Design Research and Learning Experience Design

2.1 Educational Design Research as an Iterative Process

Let's begin here by defining the concept of educational design research. It's research conducted in educational settings whose aim is to iteratively design and develop solutions to educational problems. Educational design research produces usable knowledge—educational interventions and products—derived from the participants' insights and shares this knowledge with other practitioners. It also involves empirical investigations. Through these, educational design research generates theoretical knowledge to help the work of other educators. (McKenney & Reeves 2018, 6)

McKenney and Reeves' generic model for conducting educational design research (Figure 4) can be used as a reference framework for my *AI Corner* project. The model includes three core phases, each with two sides where theory and practice interrelate. The process is iterative, as is represented by the arrows in Figure 4. The trapezoid at the top, as McKenney and Reeves explain, “represents implementation and spread, showing that interaction with practice is present from the start, and that the scope increases over time.” (McKenney & Reeves 2018, 83)

Figure 4. Generic model for educational design research (McKenney & Reeves 2018, 83)

McKenney and Reeves (2018, 86–87) further explain that following their model produces two outputs: interventions and theoretical understanding. While interventions impact teaching practice, they also contribute indirectly to theoretical understanding. The process is iterative: the empirical findings of a project contribute to theoretical understanding and, indirectly, to practice when the ideas are being shared and used to design future interventions. This is what I hope the *AI Corner* capstone project will accomplish.

My project was informed by McKenney and Reeves' model for conducting educational design research as follows. In the analysis and exploration phase, my goal was to gain a better understanding of GenAI tools. To achieve this, I participated in in-house and other training sessions and webinars on GenAI, I followed professional social media and other discussions on GenAI and higher education, I collected and reviewed related literature and began compiling a preliminary list of readings and references, and I gathered data from LAB and LUT students about their understanding and use of AI tools. In the design and construction phase, my goal was to create the *AI Corner* module on the LUT Moodle learning management platform. Finally, in the evaluation and reflection phase, I conducted empirical testing by piloting *AI Corner* with a small group of LAB and LUT students and gathered exit feedback from the students.

2.2 Learning Experience Design for Engaging Learning

Considering the design and construction phase in McKenney and Reeves' (2018) generic model for educational design research, to plan and create *AI Corner*, my project was informed by the general concept of learning experience design, as well as certain learning design models and concepts.

Let's first define learning experience design. According to Wolfe-Burleson, Herron, and Chaves (2022, xiii), the concept originated during World War II when the military needed training materials. In 1954, B.F. Skinner's paper, *The Science of Learning and the Art of Teaching*, introduced the concept of programmed instructional materials, and others, such as Robert Gagné, later expanded upon this. Today, many synonymous expressions are in use: learning experience design, learning engineering, and learning architecture. Despite such conceptual ambiguity, as Schmidt and Huang (2021, 141–144) explain, learning experience design can be defined as being connected to learner-centered design and user experience design. It emphasizes the role of learners, the design of learning interventions, and the interconnectedness of learners, learning interventions, and the learning context.

In addition to being an educator, any higher education teacher at a Finnish university or university of applied sciences must, at least to some extent, act as a learning experience designer to plan, develop, and teach their courses. Supporting this, Wolfe-Burleson, Herron, and Chaves (2022, xiii), for instance, point out that “often it is teachers who are creating engaging educational experiences for their students daily and can make use of instructional design principles.”

In Finnish higher education, the Digivisio 2030 Program aligns with the idea of teachers as creators of engaging educational experiences. The program website explains that “Digivisio strengthens the role of the teacher as a producer of high-quality content and as a facilitator of internationally renowned study experiences.” Digivisio is a joint program of all 37 Finnish higher education institutions that aims to “create a future for learning that benefits higher education institutions, learners and our society as a whole.” (Digivisio 2024) To help Finnish higher education teachers achieve such goals, Digivisio offers teacher training courses.

As part of my professional development, and my *AI Corner* capstone project, I completed a 3-ECTS Digivisio course, *Digivisio – Learning Design and Instruction*³, during the autumn semester of 2024. The course has these two objectives:

- To provide tools to design learner-centered, pedagogically high-quality courses.
- To help understand the importance of creating pedagogical scripts; to provide guidance for creating high-quality learning experiences. (Digivisio – Oppimisen muotoilu 2024)

Completing the course requires participants to work on a pedagogical development task and provide peer feedback. The work is organized around four online sessions:

- 1) Getting started
- 2) Workshop 1: Learner-Centered Design
- 3) Workshop 2: Designing Good-Quality Learning Experiences
- 4) Workshop 3: Presenting Development Tasks⁴

Each workshop requires participants to complete activities and become acquainted with learning experience design models. For instance, my *AI Corner* design work was informed by FITech’s⁵ learning design process shown in Figure 5. I took full advantage of the course and created much of the content I present in Chapters 3.4 and 4.1 during the course.

Figure 5. FITech’s learning design process (FITech 2025)

³ In Finnish: *Digivisio – Oppimisen muotoilu ja ohjaus*

⁴ In Finnish: 1) Aloitus: Miten pääsen alkuun, 2) Ensimmäinen työpaja: Oppija keskiössä, 3) Toinen työpaja: Laadukkaan oppimiskokemuksen tuottaminen, 4) Kolmas työpaja: Kehittämistehtävien esittelyt

⁵ FITech is joint organization by seven Finnish universities of technology, Technology Industries Finland, the Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland TEK, University of Jyväskylä, and University of Eastern Finland

3 AI Corner: Project Description

3.1 Identifying a Need: AI as a Recurring Theme

The release of ChatGPT-like GenAI tools has begun to upend higher education, largely because academic performance has traditionally been demonstrated through written work, be it essays, literature reviews, reflective writing (e.g., learning journals), or research reports (e.g., theses). Writing and overall communication competence are often emphasized in higher education contexts, “because nearly every industry now identifies communication skills—written, visual, and spoken—as primary qualifications when hiring new employees”, as Dobrin (2023, 99) states. GenAI’s disruptive impact on higher education, specifically writing assignments, was recognized immediately, as only a week after the release of ChatGPT, The Atlantic published an ominously titled article, *The College Essay is Dead*, whose opening paragraph warned that “Nobody is prepared for how AI will transform academia” (Marche 2022).

Questions concerning AI also remain a recurring theme of higher education pedagogy in Finland. For instance, AI was listed among the themes of the annual Higher Education Pedagogy Seminar, Pedaforum 2024, at Häme University of Applied Sciences in June 2024 (Image 1).

Image 1. Pedaforum 2024’s themes (Pedaforum 2024, screenshot)

The need for further discussion on GenAI’s impact on higher education pedagogy and its integration into teaching remains topical in Finland. At the time of writing this report in early 2025, *the UAS Journal – Journal of Finnish Universities of Applied Sciences* has a call for papers focused on higher education pedagogy for its 2/2025 issue, to be published in May 2025. Among the issue’s themes, the call for papers includes the following question about artificial intelligence: “How will the utilisation of artificial intelligence change the pedagogy of higher education institutions?” (UAS Journal 2025).

AI remains topical at the Pedaforum seminar. As shown in Image 2, it's again among the key themes of the event in June 2025 organized at Metropolia University of Applied Sciences.

Digitalisation and Artificial Intelligence Now and in the Future

Digitalisation and AI significantly influence the forms, objectives, evaluation, and concerns of learning and teaching. As tools evolve, higher education institutions need innovative experiments and solutions. Have you addressed any of the following topics in your work or research?

- What are the future digital solutions for teaching and learning in higher education?
- How does AI transform teaching in higher education?
- How does AI reshape assessment practices in higher education?
- How does AI change the competence requirements of teachers and students?
- What ethical considerations must be taken into account when utilising AI in higher education?
- How should higher education institutions address changing demands regarding data security?

Image 2. Pedaforum 2025's themes (Pedaforum 2025, screenshot)

In the specific context of language and communication pedagogy, my home organization, the joint Language Centre of LAB University of Applied Science and LUT University, will host the Language Centre Days of Finnish University Language Centres in May 2025. It's no surprise that the list of themes includes artificial intelligence, as shown in Image 3.

Language and technology

- Studying online vs in-class
- Hybrid teaching
- The opportunities and challenges of artificial intelligence
- Artificial intelligence and evaluation

Image 3. Language Centre Days 2025's themes (Language Centre Days 2025, screenshot)

Discussion around AI and higher education language pedagogy will continue in the autumn of 2025. For instance, the annual Languages and Communication Teaching Days seminar, to be held in October 2025 at Oulu University of Applied Sciences, lists AI among its themes, as shown in Image 4.

4. Evolving methods of learning and teaching

- The impact of artificial intelligence on language and communication learning, assessment, and work-life skill requirements
- Digital solutions for language and communication teaching and learning
- Higher education community supporting evolving language and communication pedagogy

Image 4. Language and Communication Teaching Days' themes (Oamk 2025, screenshot)

As the examples I've given here reveal, Finnish educators have clearly recognized that GenAI is changing and challenging higher education. Various Finnish higher education events have emphasized, and continue to focus on, the need to reflect on how to best incorporate GenAI into higher education pedagogy and, more specifically, language and communication teaching.

My *AI Corner* capstone project contributes to this. In short, *AI Corner* is an asynchronous online course (1 ECTS) focused on AI basics in English, AI ethics and AI risks in English, and leveraging GenAI for professional writing in English. To plan and develop *AI Corner*, I needed to understand my students' perspectives, so I'll next explore their opinions and use of AI tools before proceeding to discuss the *AI Corner* project and module in detail.

3.2 Students' Use of AI at LAB and LUT

Before beginning to design the *AI Corner* module, I surveyed LAB and LUT students during the early spring semester of 2024. I shared my questionnaire (Appendix 1) with 581 active students enrolled in several of my and my colleagues' English courses. Overall, 91 students responded, resulting in a response rate of about 16%. While the first set of questionnaire items (statements 1–6) collected background information, the main set (7–15) included statements related to AI tools that were answered using scales such as Often, Sometimes, Rarely, Never, or Yes, Partly, No", along with boxes for open-ended comments.

I should note that, because the survey was based on convenience sampling, and because the total combined population of LAB and LUT students is approximately 17,000, my sample is not statistically representative. Still, I do consider the survey findings indicative and valuable as background for designing *AI Corner*. Let's next discuss some key findings.⁶

Questionnaire items 1–5 collected general background information about the respondents: 1) Home university: LAB or LUT, 2) Unit or Faculty: LAB, 3) Faculty or School: LUT, 4) Course enrolment: LUT, and 5) Course enrolment: LAB. Of the 91 respondents, 48 (53%) were LAB students and 43 (47%) were LUT students. Of the 48 LAB students, 44 (92%) were business students, and the remaining 4 (8%) were engineering students. Among the LUT students, 13 (35%) were business students, and 24 were engineering students either from the School Engineering Science (19 respondents, 51%) or the School of Energy Systems (5 respondents, 14%). The respondents were enrolled in various ESP or other English language courses: *Eng-*

⁶ I have discussed some of the findings earlier in Guedra (2024b).

lish for Work, English for Professional Communication, Writing for Digital Media, Business Writing, English for Professional Development, Yhteiskunta- ja viestintätieteiden tekstitaidot⁷, Academic Writing, and English Prep Course.

In questionnaire item 6, *My average writing skill level in English*, my aim was to determine the respondents' average writing skill level in English according to the CEFR⁸ scale (A1-C2), in which A1 represents beginner level and C2 represents full proficiency. As Figure 6 shows, nearly 40% (35) placed their writing skill at the B2 (upper-intermediate) level and 26% (24) at the C1 (advanced level). This aligns with the typical ESP learner profile, as B2 is the expected level for most ESP courses (see e.g., Tarnopolsky 2015, 157).

Figure 6. Average writing skill levels in English (Q6)

Item 7, *I know the following AI tools*, prompted the respondents to identify which AI tools they knew of. The item listed 20 GenAI (or similar tools), such as ChatGPT 3.5, ChatGPT 4.0 (subscription-based at the time), Google's Bard (Gemini), Microsoft's Bing (Copilot), and Grammarly. Figure 7 shows part of the results. About 86% (78) were familiar with ChatGPT 3.5, and nearly 60% (54) were familiar with Grammarly. Grammarly likely ranked second because some of my colleagues and I actively instruct its use. These results reveal that students know of, and likely use, the most common GenAI tools.

⁷ A multilingual course co-instructed by an English teacher, a Swedish teacher, and a Finnish teacher.

⁸ Common European Framework of Reference for Languages

Figure 7. Familiarity with AI tools (Q7)

I also wanted to examine how frequently LAB and LUT students use GenAI tools for English coursework. Questionnaire item 8 asked the respondents to rate 16 statements about the frequency of AI tool usage on a four-point scale: Often, Sometimes, Rarely, Never.

The statements in item 8 addressed various uses of AI: brainstorming coursework; understanding coursework instructions; getting feedback on coursework; checking coursework for grammatical mistakes; checking coursework for typos and spelling mistakes; checking coursework for punctuation mistakes; summarizing source text; understanding source text; editing the tone and style of coursework; generating complete paragraphs; generating complete essays or other texts; translating passages; generating presentation materials; generating images for coursework; generating videos; and generating audio for coursework.

Figure 8 presents a graph of item 8 results, which groups the Often and Sometimes responses. Nearly half (45%) had often or sometimes used AI tools for brainstorming coursework ideas, about one third (28%) had often or sometimes used AI tools to better understand coursework instructions, and about one fifth (22%) had often or sometimes used AI tools to get feedback on their coursework. Moreover, over half (56%) had often or at least sometimes used AI tools to check coursework for grammatical mistakes or for typos and spelling mistakes (58%), while nearly half (45%) had often or sometimes used AI tools to check coursework for punctuation mistakes. One fourth (25%) had often or sometimes used AI tools to better understand source text in English, and about one fifth (22%) had used AI tools to translate text passages for coursework in English.

The final seven of Item 8 statements concerned the use of AI tools to generate complete content for coursework. For instance, only about one out of ten (8%) reported having often or sometimes generated complete paragraphs and even fewer (4%) reported having generated complete essays or other longer texts. Although these low percentages suggest low levels of misuse and, for an educator, appear promising, they should be interpreted with caution. Despite the questionnaire being answered anonymously, it can't be concluded with certainty that all respondents felt safe admitting their use of AI tools for generating complete content.

Figure 8. Use AI tools for coursework and studying in English (Q8)

Questionnaire item 9 collected open-ended comments (34 responses) about the use of AI tools for coursework in English. Some of the comments are shown in Table 3 (see Appendix 1 for the complete questionnaire and all open-ended comments for questionnaire item 9). Most comments reveal that the respondents were somewhat critical of and thoughtful about the use of

AI tools for coursework. They mention appropriate uses such as grammar checking and proof-reading but also express caution. For instance, it is emphasized that AI tools aren't perfect, and the respondents don't want AI tools to do their work for them. For an educator, this is promising, as it's feared that learners might offload their critical thinking and become dependent on GenAI tools (see e.g., Gerlich 2025). The open-ended comments suggest that the respondents were aware of both the potential benefits and pitfalls of using AI tools. These results seem to indicate that students are actively thinking about how to use GenAI tools responsibly but also want to preserve authentic learning experiences.

Table 3. Comments on the use of AI for coursework in English (Q9)

It can be a useful tool when used properly for studies. The problem for me is that AI is still not perfect and I think it should be used for bigger projects as it can go horribly wrong. For proofreading or checking for mistakes in large texts might be something useful. Also if you need to study large number of materials for some projects you could use AI to check on the documents or ask for summaries of large texts so that you know what you should read and what not.
I see AI tools useful for brainstorming and creating pictures. I think that using too much AI won't help student to learn English which should be the main agenda in English course. AI tools should be assistant tools to learn. More not opposite.
I use AI to help me get better and sometimes to be more efficient but I don't want to let AI do all the work for me.
It can be a helpful tool to check the work for mistakes (grammatical, typos, etc.) and also be of help for doing part of the work that is not the main task or point of the assignment like generating illustrations for a presentation. However, it should not be violated and only used when needed — not completing everything with AI.
AI tools help to improve grammar and punctuation use. Using AI for idea generation could be a good way to get creative ideas. But the drawbacks are using AI a lot, which makes the brain lazy.
It is useful but I don't use it much. There is a certain satisfaction when you read books and do research on your own without these AI Tools.
I just use AI to get idea about the question or get the format for example how essays can be written. But I never copy and paste from AI.
It's efficient to use for Brainstorming. Though sometimes it fails to provide the right answers.
AI is good as long as it is used in a smart way.
AI is very useful to get ideas for some assignments and that is how I normally use it. It is easy to take the idea or somehow modify the idea. AI can be very useful to correct spelling but I think it might give a wrong idea about someone's skills because you can just put something in for example Gemini and the AI will give you a perfect text back.
I think using AI to highlight mistakes and making some single phrases can be instructive. I have learned to notice some typical mistakes I make while writing by using Grammarly's mistake correction and I have learned by seeing them corrected.
AI tools help a lot to do English or any other courses tasks but I never use AI's developed texts in straight. I always read the text and do some changes I need.
Very useful in certain situations for example in order to correct grammar and punctuation errors.
AI is a good tool to spellcheck. But I do not want to use it to create English text from the scratch, because I think I will not learn anything that way.

Questionnaire item 10 was designed to examine students' knowledge of certain AI vocabulary and terms in English. It included eight statements using the following AI-related words or terms: "generative AI," "hallucinate," "anthropomorphized," "prompting," "Large Language Model," "reinforcement learning," "AI ethics," and "AI Literacy." The respondents rated the statements on a three-point scale: Yes, Partly, No.

Figure 9 presents a graph of item 10 answers, in which the Yes and Partly responses have been combined. Nearly nine out of ten (89%) knew or partly knew what “generative AI” means, about eight out of ten (81%) knew or partly knew what “AI ethics” means, and nearly two-thirds knew or partly knew what “hallucinate” (65%) and “AI Literacy” (62%) mean. Just over half knew or partly knew what “prompting” (57%) and “reinforcement learning” (53%) mean. The least familiar terms among the respondents were “anthropomorphized” and “Large Language Model”. Only a little over one-third of the respondents answered that they knew or partly knew what “anthropomorphized” (40%) or “Large Language Model” (38%) mean. Based on these results, it seems that, although students are familiar with certain AI vocabulary in English (e.g., generative AI and AI ethics), they might be less familiar with some of the more specialized terminology.

Figure 9. Knowledge of basic AI concepts (Q10)

Questionnaire item 11 listed seven statements concerning AI ethics, university policies, and the use of AI by teachers to provide feedback and do automated grading. The respondents rated the statements on a three-point scale: Yes, Partly, No. Figure 10 presents a graph in which Yes and Partly responses have been combined.

Nine out of ten were familiar or partly familiar with data privacy issues (90%), using AI tools to responsibly generate content (89%), and the university’s AI policies (93%). Approximately two-thirds responded that teachers had either fully or partly instructed them on how to use AI tools

(69%), while two-thirds also responded that they knew or partly knew how to cite the use of AI tools for coursework (68%).

The final two statements of item 11 examined students' views on teachers' use of AI tools for providing feedback and for automated grading. Nearly three-quarters (74%) would fully or partially accept if teachers used AI tools for providing feedback. Approximately half (51%) would fully or partially accept if teachers used AI tools for automated grading. These results are somewhat surprising to me, as they seem to indicate that students might be willing to accept teachers outsourcing assignment feedback and grading to AI tools.

Figure 10. Knowledge of/Opinions on AI policies (Q11)

Questionnaire item 12 collected open-ended comments (13 responses) on basic AI concepts and AI policies. A few comments stand out (see Appendix 1 for the complete questionnaire and all open-ended comments for questionnaire item 12):

- *Some teachers importantly emphasize that excessive use of AI in school tasks is forbidden.*
- *I think there needs to be more clear instructions on how AI is allowed to be used and how to cite the use.*
- *AI policy should be strict and more detailed.*
- *The teachers should also at least quickly check the papers submitted and not fully rely on AI.*

These comments indicate that, already at the time of the survey in spring 2024, some guidelines were in place and some teachers were addressing the use of AI tools in their instruction. The comments also suggest that, although automated assignment feedback and grading might be acceptable, a human teacher is still often needed and preferred to remain involved.

Questionnaire item 13 aimed to find out what the respondents think about using AI tools for communication—specifically writing—in English. It included twelve statements answered on a five-point scale: Strongly agree, Agree, Not sure, Disagree, Strongly disagree. Figure 11 presents a graph that combines the Strongly agree and Agree responses, as well as the Disagree and Strongly disagree responses.

Seven out of ten (72%) strongly agreed or agreed that knowing how to use AI tools is an important professional skill. Close to two-thirds (62%) strongly agreed or agreed that it is ethically acceptable to use AI tools for work, while two-thirds (67%) strongly agreed or agreed that becoming reliant on AI tools is a risk. When it comes to evaluating AI-generated content in English, only one-third (32%) strongly agreed or agreed that this is easy, while nearly one-quarter (22%) strongly disagreed or disagreed with the statement and nearly half (46%) were not sure. These results seem to reveal a skills gap: students recognize the importance of GenAI tools but struggle with evaluating AI-generated content.

The respondents also considered that AI tools can help improve writing in English. A little over half (56%) strongly agreed or agreed that using AI tools helps make their writing smoother in English, while about half strongly agreed or agreed that using AI tools makes them feel more confident writers in English (49%) and that using AI tools to help write in English can reduce stress (48%). Almost two-thirds (63%) strongly agreed or agreed that using AI tools helps make their writing in English grammatically better. Based on these results, students seem to value GenAI tools for improving the technical aspects of their writing in English, and using the tools may also bring some psychological benefits. In some statements, the Not sure responses have relatively high percentages (e.g., 35%, 39%, 46%, 52%). This could suggest that many students are still forming their opinion about the use of AI tools to help communicate in English.

Figure 11. Opinions about AI tools and their use to communicate in English (Q13)

Questionnaire item 14 concerned AI risks and included four statements answered on a five-point scale: Strongly agree, Agree, Not sure, Disagree, Strongly disagree. Figure 12 shows a graph that combines the Strongly agree and Agree responses, as well as the Disagree and Strongly disagree responses.

Nearly eight out of ten strongly agreed or agreed that copyright (77%) and data privacy (78%) are a risk. However, a little over half (55%) were not sure whether carbon dioxide emissions are a risk, and half (50%) were not sure whether using outsourced workers to train AI models is a risk. Apparently, students are aware of copyright and data privacy risks but are less familiar with AI's impact on the environment and labor practices.

Figure 12. Opinions about AI risks (Q14)

Questionnaire item 15 collected open-ended comments (14 responses) about the use of AI tools to communicate in English and about AI risks. Some of the comments are presented in Table 4 (see Appendix 1 for the complete questionnaire and all open-ended comments for questionnaire item 15). The respondents recognized AI tools as helpful but also identified risks: while AI tools can assist, relying on them may bring negative effects. As with the comments in item 9, from an educator's perspective, this is promising: students actively reflect on the benefits and risks of AI tools.

Table 4. Comments on the use of AI tools for English and on AI risks (Q15)

AI tools can help you, but you need to be careful not to violate any copyright laws.
A nice tool with gigantic risks.
AI is already in use in all over The World. Even Finnish journalist use it as their daily basis tasks. I see it a good assistant tool but as a worker. There are several risks too. One is that you become to write too similar text and your content lose interests. Secondly you might make too simple text structures or The plot of The text is missing. You might use by mistake wrong and unverified sources or data.
It helps in searching for information, but not always
AI tends to make up facts, like that squirrels lay eggs, so you need to check the information through carefully.
Well, AI tools and their use to communicate in English can be helpful especially if it is not your mother tongue. It will help in a way to improve one's knowledge in English. But at the same time, using it too much will make the person lazy and will become more dependent on it. One of the risks is the data that they collected may be used against a person.

Overall, my spring 2024 survey results indicate that LAB and LUT students are familiar with GenAI tools and use them for some help when doing coursework in English. They recognize the importance of knowing about GenAI tools for work and know AI terms in English but might be less familiar with some of the more technical terminology. They are cautious about using GenAI and are specifically worried about copyright issues and data privacy risks.

I began working on the *AI Corner* module in late spring 2024 after completing the survey introduced here. The findings provided some foundation and direction for this work. The next chapter introduces the *AI Corner* project timeline in detail.

3.3 AI Corner Project Timeline

While I began my DigiErko studies and began brainstorming the *AI Corner* project in autumn 2023, and continued working on it until early 2025, my interest in AI and its developments predated all this, even the launch of ChatGPT in late 2022 (Figure 13).

In autumn 2021, an educational technology specialist, Sami Simpanen, working at LAB/LUT at the time, shared a link to an online article (Robitzski 2020) on the organization’s intranet about a student who had successfully passed master’s level courses using GPT-2 to write some of his coursework. Reading this made me realize that language and communication instructors in higher education would soon need to address such developments. Following the launch of ChatGPT in November 2022, I immediately began participating in AI-focused training sessions and webinars in early 2023 to gain more understanding.

Figure 13. Timeline: Pre- and early DigiErko

As I’ve outlined in Figure 14, in addition to starting the DigiErko studies in autumn 2023, creating a project plan and pitching my *AI Corner* project idea, I continued attending AI-focused training sessions and webinars throughout the semester to stay up to date. I found one of the webinars particularly useful as it featured Professor Sidney Dobrin as a guest speaker. Dobrin had recently published a book, *AI and Writing*, which later became one of my main sources for designing *Module 3: AI Writing in AI Corner*.

I also worked with my colleagues on certain AI themes. Several of them, for instance, agreed to act as my sparring partners for the project and shared my Students' Use of AI 2024 questionnaire link with their students. What's more, I and two of my colleagues, Ella Hujala and Vesa Koskela, were tasked to plan and create an AI policies document for the English teachers' team. We worked on this and published the *English Team AI Policies* document in late spring 2024, now available to our colleagues.

I continued participating in several AI-focused webinars throughout spring 2024 and administered the survey about students' use of AI at LAB and LUT, whose results I've presented in the preceding chapter. I also wrote a little about AI themes and, as a result, published an AI literacy-related blog post (Guedra 2024a) and a short article about the unreliability of AI detectors (Guedra 2024c) on LAB's website.

After conducting my spring-2024 survey, I began designing and creating *AI Corner* materials in late spring 2024 and presented some of the survey results to my colleagues during our Language Centre Development Days' trip to Tallinn.

Figure 14. Timeline: DigiErko, autumn 2023 and spring 2024

As Figure 15 shows, autumn 2024 was also eventful. I kept participating in AI and education webinars and, again, presented some of my survey results to LAB teaching staff in workshop sessions at LAB DigiPeda Days, an event organized on both campuses (Lahti/Lappeenranta) by the @Peda team (of which I'm a member) and the LAB/LUT Opetushelp team. The @Peda

team consists of teachers from the various departments and units of LAB who are interested in improving teaching practice throughout the organization, while Opetushelp is an internal support team that helps teaching staff with pedagogical solutions and use of educational technology such as Moodle. And I also wrote a short article to publish some of the survey results (Guedra 2024c) in the Language Centre's annual publication, *Kielivirtaa Saimaalta*.

I continued working on the *AI Corner* module materials and designing the module on Moodle, participated in the *Digivisio – Learning Design and Instruction* course to further develop the module, and piloted the module in late November and early December of autumn 2024. My *AI Corner* pilot exit feedback survey also gathered some data on students' opinions and use of AI tools by incorporating some of the questionnaire items from the earlier spring 2024 survey. I'll discuss the pilot run and introduce the exit feedback survey results in Chapter 4.3.

At the end of autumn 2024, I was asked to become the Language Centre's representative and a member of the LAB AI Expert Group. Currently, the expert group's main task is to gather information for the LAB/LUT AI Roadmaps. Later, when the Roadmaps are being implemented, the expert group likely begins gathering further ideas and feedback. (Mäkelä 2024)

Figure 15. Timeline: DigiErko, autumn 2024

I'm completing the *AI Corner* project at the moment of writing this in early spring 2025. I'll introduce my plans for *AI Corner* and other near-future steps in Chapter 5. The next chapter, however, presents my project audience analysis, mostly completed during the *Digivisio – Learning Design and Instruction* course in the autumn of 2024.

3.4 Audience Analysis: Target Groups

Even though I'd conducted the *Students' Use of AI* survey earlier in spring 2024 as background for the *AI Corner* module, coursework during the *Digivisio – Learning Design and Instruction course* in autumn 2024 helped me further reflect on *AI Corner's* audiences and develop more nuanced ideas about its potential target groups.

To analyze target groups, I applied the Target Groups template provided in FITech's *Learning Design Toolkit v 2.0* (Huhtanen 2019) with some minor revisions. Table 5 includes my target group analysis, which largely draws on my reflections and experience of being a higher education English language and communication teacher since 2008, as well as the results of my *Students' Use of AI* survey.

Table 5. Target group analysis

Target groups	Mainly first-year bachelor's degree students at LAB.	Mainly first-year bachelor's degree students at LUT.	Anyone interested in GenAI basics in English.
Characteristics	<p>Average age ranges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 18–23, 25–45 <p>Educational backgrounds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High school/vocational University degree Some university <p>Cultural backgrounds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finnish Mixed international <p>Average language skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heterogeneous; mostly B1 to B2 <p>Prior knowledge of AI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some but may vary 	<p>Average age ranges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 18–22 <p>Educational backgrounds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mostly high school University degree Some university <p>Cultural backgrounds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mostly Finnish, some mixed international <p>Average language skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heterogeneous; mostly B2 <p>Prior knowledge of AI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some but may vary 	<p>Age ranges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nearly any age 16+ <p>Educational backgrounds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any education <p>Cultural backgrounds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finnish Mixed international <p>Average language skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heterogeneous <p>Prior knowledge of AI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some but likely varies extensively
What motivates learners in this target group?	<p>The course is 100% online and asynchronous.</p> <p>To learn GenAI basics and how to use GenAI tools responsibly for studies and work.</p> <p>To earn 1 ECTS.</p>	<p>The course is 100% online and asynchronous.</p> <p>To learn GenAI basics and how to use GenAI tools responsibly for studies and work.</p> <p>To earn 1 ECTS.</p>	<p>The course is 100% online and asynchronous.</p> <p>To get basic information about GenAI tools in English.</p>
What might be difficult for learners?	<p>Learners with lower than CEFR B2 English skills may find parts of the course challenging.</p> <p>Completing <i>AI Corner</i> requires self-initiative, independent study, and time management.</p> <p>Learners expecting contact teaching may find <i>AI Corner</i> challenging or demotivating.</p>	<p>Learners with lower than CEFR B2 English skills may find parts of the course challenging.</p> <p>Completing <i>AI Corner</i> requires self-initiative, independent study, and time management.</p> <p>Learners expecting contact teaching may find <i>AI Corner</i> challenging or demotivating.</p>	<p>Competing <i>AI Corner</i> requires very good English skills.</p> <p>Completing <i>AI Corner</i> requires self-initiative, independent study, and time management.</p> <p>Learning to use Moodle.</p>
How will learners find the course?	<i>AI Corner</i> is either integrated into an English course the learner is enrolled in or offered as a standalone 1-ECTS course on the opin.fi platform.	<i>AI Corner</i> is either integrated into an English course the learner is enrolled in or offered as a standalone 1-ECTS course on the opin.fi platform.	<i>AI Corner</i> is offered as a standalone 1-ECTS course on the opin.fi platform.

To summarize the target group analysis in Table 5, I designed the *AI Corner* module with three primary audiences in mind: primarily first-year bachelor's degree students at both LAB and LUT, and anyone interested in learning GenAI basic in English.

The first two audience cohorts—first-year LAB and LUT students—likely share the same goal: to learn GenAI basics and how to use GenAI tools responsibly for studies and work. While learners in these two cohorts likely have at least some prior knowledge of and experience with using GenAI tools, their familiarity may vary considerably. Learners in both cohorts share similar motivations for taking *AI Corner*, but they differ in some key characteristics. LUT students are generally a more uniform group, while LAB students likely come from a broader age range and have more heterogeneous educational and cultural profiles.

The third audience cohort is the most internally diverse as it may include anyone interested in learning GenAI basics in English. Learners in the third cohort likely represent various age groups, educational backgrounds, and cultural contexts. Their prior knowledge of AI may vary significantly, and their average English skills are likely heterogeneous.

4 AI Corner: Designing and Piloting the Module

4.1 Designing: Pedagogical Script

As I've mentioned, I participated in the *Digivisio – Learning Design and Instruction* course in autumn 2024 to design the *AI Corner* module. One of the assignments was to create a pedagogical script. In Finnish higher education pedagogy, a pedagogical script is a planning tool that helps conceptualize and visualize a coherent learning process and how it unfolds; how learners will meet given learning objectives (see e.g., Marstio 2020, 16). A pedagogical script also includes pedagogical touchpoints, “opportunities for student engagement” (Tualaualelei et al. 2022). I created a table that includes the various sections (modules) *AI Corner* divides into, lists pedagogical touchpoints or activities in each section, and outlines what the learner should do at each point. The tables here present the *AI Corner* pedagogical script step-by-step.

Table 6 shows the introductory part of my *AI Corner* pedagogical script, with a brief background explanation, and lists the three learning outcomes of the *AI Corner* module.

Table 6. Pedagogical script: Intro and learning outcomes

Pedagogical Script: <i>AI Corner</i> (1 ECTS)	
Background <i>AI Corner</i> can be used either as a module integrated into compulsory first-year English language courses or as a standalone online course (e.g., an asynchronous MOOC).	
Learning outcomes Upon completion of <i>AI Corner</i> :	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You can define and use key terms of AI in English. You can identify AI risks and key points of AI ethics in English. You can use AI tools responsibly for professional writing in English. 	

The second part of my script, shown in Table 7, outlines the *Welcome (start here)* section of *AI Corner*. Here, the script divides into two columns. Of these, the left one lists the content, activities, and pedagogical touchpoints, while the right one explains what the learner is expected to do at each point.

Table 7. Pedagogical script: Welcome (start here)

Welcome (start here)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contact information + technical support. Learning outcomes. Welcome video (video 1:20 mins) Instructions on what to do. Instructor's announcements (forum) <i>AI Corner</i> chatbot at poe.com (link) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The student reads the instructions and learning outcomes. The student watches the welcome video. The student reads the instructor's announcements when needed. The student can access the <i>AI Corner</i> chatbot to ask about course topics.

Table 8 outlines the third section of my script: *Module 1: AI Basics*. As in the previous part, I've structured the script here in two columns. The left column includes content and activities, while the right one explains what the learner should do at each point. *Module 1: AI Basics* has four pedagogical touchpoints or activities: a questionnaire (highlighted in yellow), a discussion (highlighted in green), an interactive coursebook that includes related study materials (highlighted in light blue), and a quiz (highlighted in grey).

Table 8. Pedagogical script: Module 1: AI Basics

Module 1: AI Basics	
General instructions for Module 1.	The student reads the instructions.
Questionnaire: Your views on and use of AI tools	The student answers the questionnaire to reflect on their pre-existing understanding of AI.
Discussion: Who are you? Have you already used AI tools?	The student starts a discussion thread to introduce themselves and discusses their prior knowledge of AI. The student posts two replies to two other students' discussion threads.
Module 1: Introduction and Basics (H5P) 1.1 AI as an Idea/Concept (video, 5:20 mins) 1.2 AI as an English Language Word (video, 2:30 mins) 1.3. Some Key Terms of AI: Flashcards 1.4 Some key Terms of AI: Drag and Drop 1.5 Some AI Metaphors (video, 5:40 mins) 1.6 Generative AI (video, 6:35 mins) 1.7 Interactive Online Activities 1.8 History of AI: Timeline 1.9 Deep Dive Podcast on Section 1 (podcast, 23:30 mins) 1.10 Readings 1.11 Sources and Other Materials	The student studies the materials in the Module 1 H5P interactive coursebook. After studying the materials, the student marks the activity as done.
Quiz: Basics and Key Terms of AI in English	The student takes the quiz to test their learning of key terms of AI in English, the history of AI, and AI metaphors. The student can take the quiz as many times as needed to pass.
Quiz answer key	The student can open the quiz answer key after passing the quiz.

Module 1: AI Basics introduces foundational AI concepts and terminology, as well as some key points in the history of AI. From the learners' viewpoint, *Module 1: AI Basics* has three learning objectives: 1) to recognize what they already know about AI tools, 2) to share and discuss their

prior experiences, and 3) to recall and review what they have learned about AI terms, AI metaphors, and the history of AI.

The fourth section of my *AI Corner* pedagogical script, *Module 2: AI Ethics*, is presented in Table 9. The script again consists of two columns, one for content and activities and another one that explains what the learner needs to do. *Module 2: AI Ethics* has two pedagogical touchpoints: an interactive coursebook that includes related study materials (highlighted in light blue) and a quiz (highlighted in grey).

Table 9. Pedagogical script: Module 2: AI Ethics

Module 2: AI Ethics	
General instructions for Module 2.	The student reads the instructions.
<p style="background-color: #e0f0ff;">Module 2: AI Ethics and Risks (H5P)</p> <p>2.1 What is AI Ethics? (video, 6:30 mins)</p> <p>2.2 LAB/LUT AI Policies</p> <p>2.3 AI Risks: Part 1 (video, 6:35 mins)</p> <p>2.4 AI Risks: Part 2 (video, 5:25 mins)</p> <p>2.5 AI Risks: Part 3 (video, 5:30 mins)</p> <p>2.6 Interactive Online Materials</p> <p>2.7 Flowchart: Safe or Unsafe to use GenAI?</p> <p>2.8 Deep Dive Podcast on Section 2 (podcast 15:45 mins)</p> <p>2.9 Readings</p> <p>2.10 Sources and Other Materials</p>	<p>The student studies the materials in the Module 2 H5P interactive coursebook.</p> <p>After studying the materials, the student marks the activity as done.</p>
<p style="background-color: #e0e0e0;">Quiz: AI Ethics and Risks</p>	<p>The student takes the quiz to test their learning about AI ethics and risks.</p> <p>The student can take the quiz as many times as needed to pass.</p>
Quiz answer key	The student can open the quiz answer key after passing the quiz.

Module 2: AI Ethics introduces the concept of AI ethics and explores several key risks involved in using AI tools. From the learner's perspective, this module has one primary learning objective: to recall and review what they have learned about AI ethics and risks.

Table 10 shows the fifth part of my *AI Corner* pedagogical script: *Module 3: AI Writing*. Similar to the previous sections, I've repeated the two-column structure. Likewise, as with the two previous modules, *Module 3: AI Writing* includes two pedagogical touchpoints: an interactive coursebook that includes related study materials (highlighted in light blue) and a quiz (highlighted in grey).

Table 10. Pedagogical script: Module 3: AI Writing

Module 3: AI Writing	
General instructions for the module.	The student reads the instructions.
Module 3: AI for Professional Communication in English (H5P)	The student studies the materials in the Module 3 H5P interactive coursebook.
3.1 Writing Process (video, 2:30 mins)	After studying the materials, the student marks the activity as done.
3.2 GenAI at the Prewriting Stage (video, 4:35 mins)	
3.3 GenAI at the Drafting Stage (video, 4:50 mins)	
3.4 GenAI at the Revising Stage (video, 4:35 mins)	
3.5 GenAI at the Editing and Proofreading Stage (video, 5:10 mins)	
3.6 Prompting: Intro (video, 1:30 mins)	
3.7 Prompting: Five Techniques (video, 5:40 mins)	
3.8 Prompting: Match Definitions: Drag and Drop	
3.9 Deep Dive Podcast: Section 3 (podcast, 15:30 mins)	
3.10 Readings	
3.11 Sources and Other Materials	
Quiz: AI for Professional Writing	The student takes the quiz to test their learning about using AI tools for professional writing and the basics of prompting.
	The student can take the quiz as many times as needed to pass.
Quiz answer key	The student can open the quiz answer key after passing the quiz.

Module 3: AI Writing introduces the conventional writing process for professional and academic communication and, moreover, discusses how GenAI can be used at the various stages of the process: in prewriting, drafting, revising, and editing and proofreading. The module also introduces prompting and some common prompting techniques: zero shot, few-shot, chain-of-thought, role, and iterative prompting. It has two specific learning objectives for learners: 1) to recall and review what they have learned about the basics of using AI tools to help with professional writing, and 2) to recall what they have learned about the basics of prompting GenAI tools.

Table 11 presents the second-to-last part of my pedagogical script, which outlines the *Activity* section. Again, similar to *Modules 1–3*, I've divided the script into two columns here. The left one lists content and activities, while the right one explains what the learner is expected to do at each point. The *Activity* section includes three pedagogical touchpoints, all structured as online discussions (highlighted in green) between learners.

Table 11. Pedagogical script: Activity

Activity	
Discussion: Studying with AI	<p>The student tests an AI tool for identifying the main points in an article.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The student looks for an article related to their studies, reads the article, and identifies five points in the article. • The student uploads the article to an AI tool and asks the AI tool to identify five points in the text. • The student reflects on the experiment. <p>The student starts a discussion to discuss the experiment. The student replies to three other students.</p>
Discussion: Writing with AI	<p>The student tests an AI tool for writing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The student writes a short passage (1 page) in English related to their studies. • The student uploads the text to an AI tool for feedback and editing. • The student reflects on the experiment. <p>The student starts a discussion to discuss the experiment. The student replies to three other students.</p>
Discussion: Generating images with AI	<p>The student tests an AI tool to generate images.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The student uploads the text passage to an AI tool and asks it to generate images based on it. • The student reflects on the experiment. <p>The student starts a discussion to discuss the experiment. The student replies to three other students.</p>

Since the *Activity* section contains three discussion activities for learners to test GenAI tools, it has several learning objectives, which vary by activity:

- **Discussion: Studying with AI:** 1) To test and evaluate an AI tool for identifying key points from an article, and 2) to share your experiences.
- **Discussion: Writing with AI:** 2) To test and evaluate an AI tool for writing, 2) to apply prompting techniques, 3) to analyze an AI tool's output, 4) to rewrite text with an AI tool, and 5) to share experiences.
- **Discussion: Generating images with AI:** 1) To test and evaluate an AI tool for image generation, 2) to apply prompting techniques, 3) to analyze an AI tool's output, and 4) to share experiences.

In short, the *Activity* section helps learners experiment with AI tools, critically reflect on the tools' output, and learn from their peers' experiences.

The last part of my *AI Corner* pedagogical script, *Completion*, is outlined in Table 12. As with the earlier parts, it follows the two-column structure. The left column lists all 11 color-coded pedagogical touchpoints or activities learners are expected to complete, while the right column

explains that they automatically receive a Moodle completion badge after they have completed all required activities.

Table 12. Pedagogical script: Completion

Completion	
<p>Moodle course completion badge.</p> <p>Activities to be completed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Questionnaire: Your views on and use of AI tools 2. Discussion: Who are you? Have you already used AI tools? 3. Section 1: Introduction and Basics (H5P) 4. Quiz: Basics and Key Terms of AI in English 5. Section 2: AI Ethics and Risks (H5P) 6. Quiz: AI Ethics and Risks 7. Section 3: AI for Professional Communication in English (H5P) 8. Quiz: AI for Professional Writing 9. Discussion: Studying with AI 10. Discussion: Writing with AI 11. Discussion: Generating images with AI 	<p>After completing all activities, the student automatically receives a completion badge that appears in their Moodle profile.</p> <p>The badge is titled 'Badges from LUT-korkeakoulut Moodle:' and features a stylized brain icon composed of blue and white geometric shapes. Below the icon, the text reads 'AI CORNER' in a bold, sans-serif font, followed by 'AI Corner Completed' in a smaller, blue font.</p>

In the next section of this report, I'll proceed to explain how I designed and created *AI Corner* using various digital tools and resources.

4.2 Designing: Digital Tools and Resources

Moodle: *AI Corner* is offered on the LUT/LAB Moodle learning management platform. As shown in Image 5, the course page is set up with Moodle's Onetopic format and arranges content into five sections or tabs: *Welcome (start here)*, *Module 1: AI Basics*, *Module 2: AI Ethics*, *Module 3: AI Writing*, and *Activity*. Learners can track their course progress in the Completion Progress bar located at the top of the page. While waiting for completion, an activity shows blue in the bar. When completed, the activity turns green.

Image 5. Course tabs and the Completion Progress bar (screenshot)

The *Welcome (start here)* section includes a link to the *AI Corner* chatbot on the Poe.com platform (see AI Tools below) and a welcome video, as well as a forum for instructor announcements.

As shown in Image 6, *Module 1: AI Basics* includes a questionnaire activity, a discussion forum activity, an H5P interactive coursebook, and a Moodle quiz activity, as well as a quiz answer key. The answer key becomes available after the learner has passed the quiz.

Module 1: AI Basics. What to do in this section?

- Complete the questionnaire activity: *Questionnaire: Your views on and use of AI tools*
- Complete the discussion activity: *Discussion: Who are you? Have you already used AI tools?*
- Study the materials in Module 1. Then, mark Module 1 as done.
- Take *Quiz 1/3: Basics and Key Terms of AI in English*.
- Move on to *Module 2: AI Ethics*. 🙌 📄

Questionnaire: Your views on and use of AI tools 📄 **To do:** Student must submit this questionnaire to complete it

Discussion: Who are you? Have you already used AI tools? 🗨️ **49 unread posts** **To do:** Start discussions: 1
Post replies: 2

H5P: Module 1. Introduction and Basics (Click to open) 📖 **Mark as done**

- Study the materials available here.
- After you have studied the materials, mark the module as done by clicking the *Mark as done* button.

Quiz: Basics and Key Terms of AI in English 📄 **To do:** Receive a grade
To do: Receive a passing grade

Quiz answer key (You can open the answer key after passing the quiz) 📄

Image 6. Module 1 (screenshot)

The questionnaire activity collects learners' prior knowledge of AI to help them reflect on the topic, and answers are visible to everyone enrolled. The discussion forum activity requires learners to start a discussion thread to introduce themselves and reflect on how they use AI tools. It also requires learners to reply to two peers. The H5P interactive coursebook, *Module 1: Introduction and Basics*, includes several videos (see below Videos), and Diffit.me-generated (see AI Tools) readings. The quiz, *Quiz: Basics and Key Terms of AI in English*, is a multiple-choice quiz about the coursebook topics.

Image 7 includes screenshots that show *Module 2: AI Ethics* and *Module 3: AI Writing*. Their layout and designs match each other, as well as those of *Module 1: AI Basics*. Applying the same design logic should help learners progress through and complete *AI Corner*.

The screenshot displays two sections of a course, Module 2 and Module 3, each with a similar layout. Each section starts with a header: "Module 2: AI Ethics. What to do in this section?" and "Module 3: AI Writing. What to do in this section?". Below the header is a list of instructions for the learner. The main content area for each module features an H5P interactive coursebook titled "Module 2. AI Ethics and Risks (Click to open)" and "Module 3. AI for Professional Communication in English (Click to open)", each with a "Mark as done" button. A quiz is listed below the coursebook, titled "Quiz: AI Ethics and Risks" and "Quiz: AI for Professional Writing", with "To do" instructions: "Receive a grade" and "Receive a passing grade". A quiz answer key is also listed, titled "Quiz answer key (You can open the answer key after passing the quiz)", which is locked and has a note: "Not available unless: The activity Quiz: AI Ethics and Risks is complete and passed" and "Not available unless: The activity Quiz: AI for Professional Writing is complete and passed".

Module 2: AI Ethics. What to do in this section?

- Study the materials in Module 2. Then, mark Module 2 as done.
- Take *Quiz 2/3: AI Ethics and Risks*
- Move on to *Module 3: AI Writing*. 🙌 ➡

H5P Module 2. AI Ethics and Risks (Click to open) 🗨 Mark as done

- Study the materials available here.
- After you have studied the materials, mark the module as done by clicking the *Mark as done* button.

Quiz: AI Ethics and Risks 📝 To do: Receive a grade
To do: Receive a passing grade

Quiz answer key (You can open the answer key after passing the quiz)

🔒 Not available unless: The activity **Quiz: AI Ethics and Risks** 📝 is complete and passed

Module 3: AI Writing. What to do in this section?

- Study the materials in Module 3. Then, mark Module 3 as done.
- Take *Quiz 3/3: AI for Professional Writing*.
- Move on to *AI Corner Activity* 🙌 ➡

H5P Module 3. AI for Professional Communication in English (Click to open) 🗨 Mark as done

- Study the materials available here.
- After you have studied the materials, mark the module as done by clicking the *Mark as done* button.

Quiz: AI for Professional Writing 📝 To do: Receive a grade
To do: Receive a passing grade

Quiz answer key (You can open the answer key after passing the quiz)

🔒 Not available unless: The activity **Quiz: AI for Professional Writing** 📝 is complete and passed

Image 7. Module 2: AI Ethics and Module 3: AI Writing (screenshot)

Module 2 and *Module 3* both include an H5P interactive coursebook, a quiz about the coursebook topics, and a quiz answer key that becomes available after the learner has passed the quiz. *Module 3*, furthermore, includes an assignment submission link: AI vs. Human Writing

(not shown in the screenshot in Image 7). The activity includes a link to a quiz available on the GPTZero⁹ website, which asks learners to identify whether certain text passages were written by a human, an AI, or both. I created and added this activity to the course page at the moment of completing this report.

The fifth and last section, *Activity*, includes three discussion forum activities: Studying with AI, Writing with AI, and Generating Images with AI (Image 8). In each activity, learners are instructed to use a GenAI tool, reflect on its use, and share their reflections with peers. To complete each discussion, learners must start their own discussion thread to post their findings and reflections and reply to their peers' posts.

Activity. What to do in this section?

- Complete the three discussion activities below.
- After you have taken the quizzes in Modules 1-3 and completed the discussion activities here, you will receive a course completion badge that will appear in your Moodle profile. **Well done!** 🎉 🏆

Discussion: Studying with AI ○	90 unread posts	To do: Start discussions: 1 To do: Post replies: 3
Discussion: Writing with AI ○	103 unread posts	To do: Start discussions: 1 To do: Post replies: 3
Discussion: Generating Images with AI ○	107 unread posts	To do: Start discussions: 1 To do: Post replies: 3

Image 8. Activity (screenshot)

Finally, I've set up the *AI Corner* Moodle page so that all activities and the coursebooks are listed in the course Completion Progress bar. When a learner has completed all required activities, they'll automatically receive a Moodle course completion badge that appears in their Moodle user profile.

⁹ GPTZero is an AI detection tool. Here is the link to the quiz: <https://gptzero.fillout.com/ai-quiz>

AI Tools: When designing and creating *AI Corner* course materials, I experimented with numerous AI tools as I'll explain in the following.

To generate video scripts for the lecture videos offered in the course materials, I used Claude 3.5 Sonnet and Gemini 1.5 Pro hosted on the Poe.com platform, as well as Microsoft Copilot. I prompted the tools to generate the scripts but curated and edited them to make sure that they are suitable and useful. I also generated some visuals for the videos with the Napkin.ai tool and *AI Corner* course page images with Ideogram.ai. Image 9 displays a screenshot of a Napkin.ai visualization in one of the videos and a screenshot showing the Ideogram.ai image in *Module 1: AI Basics* on the *AI Corner* course page.

Image 9. Napkin.ai visualization and an Ideogram.ai-generated image (screenshot)

To generate reading materials, I experimented with Diffit.me. It's a tool that generates resources based on submitted sources (e.g., links or documents) and allows the user to customize the resources, for instance, by setting an expected reading level (from 2nd grade to 11th grade+), the language (e.g., Chinese, Finnish, English, or French), and the type of reading (informational or fictional). For transparency, it cites sources using numbered footnotes. Image 10 shows a screenshot of one of the Diffit.me-generated readings in the *AI Corner* materials.

▼ **AI Ethics 1**

Generated by prompting [diffit.me](#)

Artificial intelligence (AI) has rapidly become an integral part of our lives, impacting various industries and aspects of our daily routines. From virtual assistants to self-driving cars, AI's capabilities are undeniable, but its rapid advancement has also raised serious ethical concerns. While AI holds immense potential to improve efficiency, reduce costs, and accelerate research and development, its complex and often opaque systems have sparked worries about potential societal harm. [1][2]

One of the most pressing ethical issues surrounding AI is bias. AI systems are trained on massive datasets, and if these datasets contain biases, the AI system will inherit and even amplify those biases. This can lead to discriminatory outcomes in areas like hiring, lending, and law enforcement, where AI systems are increasingly used to make decisions. [4] For example, a study found that an AI system used for online advertising campaigns was shown more to men than women, despite the campaign aiming to reach both genders equally. The reason was not due to biased data or user behavior, but rather the "economics of ad delivery," where women were considered more valuable targets for advertisers, leading to their ads being outbid. [6]

Another significant ethical concern is privacy. AI systems often require access to vast amounts of personal data, raising concerns about how this data is collected, used, and protected. The potential for privacy violations is a major ethical challenge, especially as AI systems become more sophisticated and capable of analyzing and interpreting personal information. [4] Companies like Facebook have faced scrutiny for granting access to user data to third parties, highlighting the importance of data privacy in the age of AI. [2]

Transparency and accountability are also crucial ethical considerations. Many AI algorithms, particularly deep learning models, are often referred to as "black boxes" because their decision-making processes are difficult to understand or interpret. This lack of transparency raises concerns about accountability, as it can be challenging to determine who is responsible when an AI system makes a mistake or causes harm. [4] Ensuring transparency and accountability in AI decision-making is essential for building user trust and promoting the ethical use of AI.

The increasing autonomy of AI systems also raises ethical concerns. As AI systems become more capable of making decisions without human intervention, questions arise about the potential loss of human control. This is particularly relevant in applications like autonomous vehicles and military drones, where AI systems could make life-or-death decisions. [4] The ethical implications of AI making decisions with potentially life-altering consequences are a subject of ongoing debate and require careful consideration.

The ethical challenges posed by AI are complex and multifaceted, requiring a collaborative effort from various stakeholders, including academics, government agencies, and industry actors. [5] Developing ethical principles for responsible AI use and development is crucial to ensure that AI technology benefits society while minimizing potential risks. [5] As AI continues to advance, addressing these ethical concerns is essential to ensure a future where AI is used responsibly and ethically for the betterment of humanity.

Sources

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[5] AI Ethics: What It Is and Why It Matters | Coursera
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[6] What Are the Ethical Risks of Your AI Project? - techUK
<https://www.techuk.org/resource/what-are-the-ethical-risks-of-your-ai-project.html>

Image 10. Diffit.me-generated text (screenshot)

I used Google NotebookLM, which currently runs on Google Gemini 2, to generate podcasts from my video lecture scripts and other course materials. NotebookLM enables users to upload source materials and generate audio overviews or “deep dive discussions” (i.e. podcasts) based on the uploaded materials. The generated audio features two AI hosts, a female and male voice, who discuss the materials in American English. At the time of creating the *AI Corner* materials, NotebookLM didn’t allow the user to control the audio generation process or change any of its parameters. As shown in Image 11, the podcasts are available in the H5P interactive coursebooks on the course page.

Image 11. Google NotebookLM-generated podcast (screenshot)

Finally, I created an *AI Corner* chatbot on the Poe.com platform. It allows subscribers to create chatbots by choosing the AI model the bot runs on, by writing the bot a behavioral prompt (i.e. how the bot responds to users), and by creating the bot’s knowledge base.

My *AI Corner* chatbot currently runs on GPT-4o-Mini. It’s been prompted to act as a teaching assistant whose task is to help users learn more about artificial intelligence in English and how to use AI tools responsibly for studies, professional purposes, and work. It should provide its answers in plain English and be courteous. The behavioral prompt includes *AI Corner*’s learning objectives and background information about the bot’s potential users (i.e. university students with upper-intermediate English skills on average). Regarding ethics and academic integrity, the behavioral prompt forbids the bot from generating any complete work for the user. The bot’s knowledge base includes various *AI Corner* materials (e.g., the video scripts) as well as several Creative Commons-licensed documents and books (e.g., *AI for Teachers: An Open Textbook* and UNESCO’s *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*). Image 12 shows a screenshot of the *AI Corner* chatbot.

Image 12. AI Corner chatbot on Poe.com (screenshot)

Videos: As briefly noted earlier, the H5P interactive coursebooks include short lecture videos ranging from 2 to 6 minutes. The video titles are as follows:

- Module 1: Introduction and Basics
 - AI as an Idea/Concept
 - AI as an English Language Word
 - Some AI Metaphors
 - Generative AI
- Module 2: AI Ethics and Risks
 - What is AI Ethics?
 - AI Risks: Part 1
 - AI Risks: Part 2
 - AI Risks: Part 3
- Module 3: AI Writing
 - Writing Process
 - GenAI at the Prewriting Stage
 - GenAI at the Drafting Stage
 - GenAI at the Revising Stage
 - GenAI at the Editing and Proofreading Stage
 - Prompting: Intro
 - Prompting: Five Techniques

To add some human touch rather than use an AI-generated voice, I recorded the lectures myself with Adobe Audition 2024 and used Adobe Express to design the videos. Adobe Audition is an audio workstation tool for recording and editing audio, while Adobe Express is a cloud-based design and content creation tool that allows users to use various templates and other resources and add animations and effects to make their videos more engaging. The lecture videos are embedded in the H5P interactive coursebooks through YouTube. Each lecture video has subtitles that I edited for better accuracy based on YouTube's AI-generated auto captioning. Image 13 shows a screenshot of one of the videos embedded in the Module 3 coursebook.

Image 13. Lecture video example (screenshot)

Survey tools: To collect students' views on AI tools and to gather feedback on *AI Corner*, I used the Webropol online survey tool to administer two online questionnaires. The questionnaire results are available in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2.

I also used Google Forms to track which students had successfully completed and provided feedback on *AI Corner*. More specifically, to keep the Webropol *AI Corner* exit feedback questionnaire anonymous, Google Forms was used separately to collect the participants' names and student IDs to award them 2 ECTS upon completion.

4.3 Piloting: Students' Feedback

I opened *AI Corner* for a pilot run on the LAB/LUT Moodle platform in late November 2024: it was available between November 22 and December 5, 2024. My goal was to have a group of students test the module by completing its activities and to collect exit feedback to determine

whether *AI Corner* could be published as is. Like my earlier spring-2024 questionnaire (see Chapter 3.2), the *AI Corner* exit feedback questionnaire included some items concerning students' use and knowledge of GenAI tools.

To recruit participants, some of my colleagues promoted the *AI Corner* pilot in their Moodle courses. A total of 71 students enrolled, of which 53 completed *AI Corner* and provided feedback. The students were awarded 2 ECTS for this. I administered the process as follows: 1) only those who had completed all *AI Corner* activities could access the exit feedback questionnaire, and 2) only those who had completed the exit feedback questionnaire were awarded 2 ECTS.

Questionnaire items 1–4 collected background information, the second set, items 5–7, gathered data about students' familiarity with and use of AI tools, and the third and largest set, items 8–48, gathered feedback on *AI Corner*. While the full exit feedback questionnaire and all collected answers are available in Appendix 2, this chapter highlights some key results.

Questionnaire items 1–3 collected the following background information from the respondents: 1) Home university: LAB or LUT. 2) Unit or Faculty LAB, or 3) Faculty or School: LUT. Of the 53 respondents, 47 (89%) were LAB students and only 6 (11%) were LUT students. Of the 47 LAB students, 46 (98%) were business students, and only 1 (2%) was a technology student. Among the LUT students, 3 (50%) were business students, while the remaining 3 were engineering students from the School of Engineering Science (2 respondents, 33%) and the School of Energy Systems (1 respondent, 17%). Undoubtedly, a much more heterogeneous sample would be needed to determine clear trends or draw robust conclusions.

Similar to questionnaire item 6 in the *Students' Use of AI* questionnaire in spring 2024, the aim of item 4, *My average skill level in English*, was to determine the respondents' average skill level in English according to the CEFR scale (A1-C2). A total of 72% (38) placed their skill at the B2 or C1 level: 19 (36%) reported having B2 skills and another 19 (36%) reported having C1 skills (Figure 16). With more self-reported C1-level respondents, the spread is slightly different from that in the spring 2024 questionnaire, where item 6 focused specifically on *writing skills* in English (see Figure 6 in Chapter 3.2). The difference could be because of the spring survey's focus on English writing skills specifically. However, the results, again, align closely with the expected ESP learner profile (see e.g., Tarnopolsky 2015, 157).

Figure 16. Average English skill levels (Q4)

In questionnaire item 5, I asked the respondents to identify the AI tools they were familiar with before taking *AI Corner*. Figure 17 displays the top six AI tools in terms of familiarity. Nearly 95% (50) were familiar with ChatGPT and 75% (40) with Grammarly. Copilot ranked third with 64% (34), followed by QuillBot at 36% (19), Microsoft Editor at 34% (18), and Gemini at 32% (17). Compared with the spring 2024 questionnaire results, the higher familiarity with, for example, Grammarly, QuillBot, and Microsoft Editor suggest that students might have begun to use AI tools for writing support more, or that the respondents between the surveys differ in this respect.

Figure 17. Familiarity with AI tools (Q5)

Questionnaire item 7 concerned the use of AI tools. Figure 18 presents a graph of item 7 results. It combines the Often and Sometimes responses. Close to three-quarters had often or sometimes used AI to check coursework for grammar (74%) and for typos and spelling (72%).

Nearly two-thirds (64%) had often or sometimes used AI to brainstorm coursework ideas. Close to half had often or sometimes used AI to better understand coursework instructions (51%), to check for punctuation (51%), to better understand source text (53%), or to get feedback (49%). Around one-third had often or sometimes used AI to summarize source texts (36%) or to edit the tone and style of their coursework (32%). The final seven statements focused on the use of AI tools to generate complete content. Around one-fifth (21%) had often or sometimes used AI to generate complete paragraphs, and close to one-fourth had often or sometimes used AI to generate presentation materials (27%) or images (25%). Nearly one-sixth (17%) had often or sometimes used AI to generate essays or other long texts for coursework. Finally, around one-tenth of the respondents had often or sometimes used AI to generate videos (11%) or audio (8%) for coursework.

Figure 18. Use of AI tools for coursework in English (Q7)

These results suggest that students primarily use AI tools for editing and support. Yet, compared to the spring 2024 questionnaire results many more now reported using AI tools to generate complete content. While concerning, it can't be concluded whether this indicates a trend or simply that the respondents between the two surveys happen to differ in this respect.

The main part of the questionnaire focused on collecting feedback on *AI Corner*. Most feedback was gathered using Customer Effort Score (CES), a metric commonly used to assess how easily customers can interact with a product or service. CES surveys are also often used to examine user experience and are typically designed using five- or seven-point scales, such as Likert. (See e.g., Olson 2020, 41–42.)

Although the questionnaire items covered both the usability of the course Moodle page and the course content, I applied CES throughout the questionnaire for consistency and ease of use. While most questionnaire items were answered using a five-point scale with endpoints labelled No (1) and Yes (5), the survey tool displays CES gauge charts with a single percentage. For example, in questionnaire item 8, The learning outcomes are clear, 43.4% (23) of respondents selected 5; 47.2% (25) selected 4; 7.5% (4) selected 3 (neutral or null); 1.9% (1) selected 2; and no one (0) selected 1. The item 8 CES gauge chart in Figure 19 shows a high CES percentage, 91%, which indicates that nearly all respondents found the learning outcomes clear.

Figure 19. Exit feedback: CES gauge chart for learning outcomes

In addition to the CES questionnaire items, the questionnaire included an optional open-ended field (Please elaborate/your notes) after each CES statement (see Appendix 2 for the complete questionnaire and all open-ended comments).

Table 13 summarizes the CES questionnaire items and their CES percentages (see Appendix 2 for corresponding gauge charts). Overall, the responses were positive across most items with 14 out of 16 scoring above 80%. As the percentages reveal, *AI Corner* learning outcomes (item

8: 91%) and instructions (item 30: 96%) were found clear, and the Moodle page was found easy to navigate (item 26: 94%) and visually clear (item 28: 94%). The respondents also reported having learned for what purposes to use AI tools (item 12: 92%) and about AI risks (item 14: 92%), they found the course materials interesting (item 32: 92%) and up to date (item 34: 91%), and they felt more confident using AI tools in English after taking *AI Corner* (item 38: 94%). Regarding English language learning, many reported learning new AI terminology (item 10: 83%), how to use AI tools for both studying and for writing (items 16 and 18: 85%), and how to prompt AI for better output (item 22: 87%). Many also reported having learned some basics of using AI for image generation (item 20: 79%).

The only clear outlier was item 25 about the usefulness of the *AI Corner* bot (53%). Since the bot is experimental and using it requires signing up to Poe.com, interacting with it is optional. Answering item 25 was therefore also optional. The questionnaire data about the bot's usefulness seems somewhat inconclusive. Out of the total 53 respondents, 17 reported that they had tested the bot, while 34 reported not testing it (2 respondents seem to have skipped item 25). Instead of the expected 17 respondents, 19 had responded to this questionnaire item, which likely includes two responses from respondents who had not accessed the bot.

Table 13. Exit feedback: CES percentages

Questionnaire item	CES %
8. The learning outcomes are clear.	91%
10. I have learned new AI terminology in English.	83%
12. I have learned for what purposes AI tools might be useful.	92%
14. I have learned about some of the risks of using AI tools.	92%
16. I have learned some basics of using AI tools for studying.	85%
18. I have learned some basics of using AI tools for writing in English.	85%
20. I have learned some basics of using AI tools for image generation.	79%
22. I have learned some basics of prompting AI for better output in English.	87%
26. The page is easy to navigate.	94%
28. The page is visually clear.	94%
30. The instructions (e.g. for modules, quizzes, activities) are clear.	96%
32. The materials are interesting.	92%
34. The materials are up-to-date.	91%
36. The activities are interesting.	91%
38. I feel more confident using AI tools in English after taking <i>AI Corner</i> .	94%
42. I found the AICorner chatbot useful 🗨️.	53%

Following the CES and related open-ended questionnaire items, I designed questionnaire items 46 and 47 to gather respondents' opinions about their learning of key topics after completing *AI Corner*. Item 46 focused on determining whether the respondents had learned key AI terminology in English, while item 47 measured their familiarity with privacy in the context of generative AI, responsible use of AI to generate content, the university's AI policies, and using AI tools for writing in English. Both items were answered on a three-point scale: Yes, Partly, No.

Figure 20 presents the results for questionnaire item 46. Nearly all respondents reported that, after taking *AI Corner*, they know what "AI ethics" (94%), "generative AI" (92%), and "prompting" (92%) mean. Most respondents reported that they know what "hallucinate" (83%), "weak AI" (81%), and "strong AI" (81%) mean. However, the two outliers with lower percentages are "Large Language Model" (LLM) (72%) and "anthropomorphized" (66%).

Figure 20. Exit feedback: Knowing AI terminology

Figure 21 shows the results for questionnaire item 47. After taking *AI Corner*, nearly all respondents reported that they were familiar with data privacy issues in the context of generative AI (92%); that they were familiar with using AI tools for writing in English (92%); that they were familiar with using AI tools responsibly to generate content (91%); and that they were familiar with their university's AI policies (91%).

Figure 21. Exit Feedback: Familiarity with Practical AI Applications and Policies

Finally, questionnaire item 48 measured the respondents' overall impression of *AI Corner* using a slider on a scale of 0 (Meh!) to 5 (Grrreat!), as shown in Image 14.

Image 14. Respondents' overall impression of AI Corner (screenshot)

Of the 53 respondents, 52 responded to item 48, with one respondent leaving it unanswered. Based on the responses, the average score was 4.6 and the median score was 5 (see questionnaire item 48 in Appendix 2).

Overall, I can conclude that *AI Corner* is successful as is. The CES scores reveal that the Moodle page design is clear, navigable, and engaging. The materials and activities are interesting and up to date. Most importantly, the respondents reported having learned various AI-related topics, such as understanding AI ethics and risks, and how to apply AI tools for writing in English. Based on the feedback, the respondents also improved their understanding of core AI concepts, such as generative AI, prompting, and AI ethics, as well as data privacy, responsible AI use, and using AI tools for writing.

There were two specific areas for improvement. The *AI Corner* chatbot needs more work to prove useful. In addition, while most terms were learned well, “anthropomorphism” and “Large Language Model (LLM)” stand out as two core terms that may need to be given more focus, perhaps with more examples and activities. Despite these, *AI Corner* is effective as is.

5 Recommendations, Dissemination and Use

5.1 Recommendations

The following list was generated by prompting Claude 3.7 Sonnet on the Poe.com platform. I uploaded a draft version of this report to the AI with the following instructions:

Role: Act as a research assistant. **Focus area:** Provide a list of recommendations based on the attached *AI Corner* project report draft. **Boundaries:** Only use the attached document. **Context:** I am writing an academic report about a postgraduate project titled *AI Corner* and want to add a section for recommendations.

While I've curated the list and omitted some less useful or unrealistic recommendations, or some that I've already considered, even begun to work on, the following in Table 14 is Claude 3.7 Sonnet's list of recommendations almost verbatim.

Table 14. Claude 3.7 Sonnet's list of recommendations

Content Enhancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen teaching of complex terminology like "anthropomorphized" and "Large Language Model (LLM)" which showed lower comprehension rates in student feedback. Expand the writing module to include more sample prompts and a guided AI-scaffolded writing activity. Add more practical exercises on evaluating AI-generated content, as students reported uncertainty in this area. Develop additional content on environmental impacts of AI, which showed lower awareness in surveys.
Technical Improvements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the AI Corner chatbot functionality or provide clearer guidance on its use, as it received lower effectiveness ratings. Extend quiz time limits from 15 to 20 minutes as suggested in student feedback. Fix identified navigation issues, particularly clarifying question formats in Module 1 questionnaire.
Pedagogical Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce the number of required discussion replies from three to one or two per activity as suggested in student feedback. Incorporate more industry-specific examples showing professional use of GenAI in different fields. Develop a more comprehensive assessment model for measuring AI literacy development.
Future Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a feedback mechanism for continuous improvement after full implementation. Consider developing a more advanced follow-up module (AI Corner 2) for students wanting to deepen their knowledge. Develop companion modules for specific disciplines (e.g., AI in Business Writing, AI in Technical Documentation). Create an AI literacy assessment tool that could be used both before and after the module to measure impact.
Research Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a longitudinal study on how AI literacy impacts student writing performance. Compare ESP learning outcomes between students who completed AI Corner and those who didn't. Analyze how different prompting strategies impact ESP learners' ability to use GenAI effectively.

Being mostly in my immediate control, I'll begin working on some of the content enhancements, technical improvements, and the pedagogical approach in the near future. However, while highly interesting and motivating, beginning to work on the recommendations for future development and research would require organizational support and resources, and therefore discussions with the Language Centre management.

5.2 Project Dissemination Efforts and Plans

Regarding project dissemination, in addition to some of the steps I've already taken and described in Chapter 3.3, I'll outline some of the planned near-future steps next.

I've begun sharing my project at various internal sessions in my home organization. LAB has launched an internal pedagogical development initiative called *Future Learning*. Its main goal is to update curricula and help teachers design learner-centered educational experiences to better meet workplace needs¹⁰ (Future Learning 2025). I participated in a *Future Learning* webinar for LAB staff in mid-February 2025 where I introduced the *AI Corner* module and parts of its design process based on my coursework in the *Digivisio – Learning Design and Instruction* course.

Building on my *Future Learning* webinar presentation, I'll be participating in two other internal webinars, one in Finnish and another one in English, organized by the LAB/LUT Opetushelp team and aimed at both LAB and LUT staff members. My role is to deliver a brief presentation about the *AI Corner* module, specifically how I've utilized AI tools to help design and create the module (see Chapter 4.2 about this in this report).

Additionally, I've contacted Markus Mäkelä, the LAB/LUT Head of AI responsible for developing the *LUT and LAB AI Roadmaps*, about the *AI Corner* module. He maintains an intranet page titled *Artificial Intelligence at LUT and LAB* that features a list of ongoing pilot AI projects at the two universities. The page now also lists *AI Corner* among the ongoing pilots.

Beyond these intra-organizational dissemination efforts, I'm planning to present the project, or some parts of it, at two or three seminar events. In May 2025, at the Language Centre Days of Finnish Universities, I'll be organizing a workshop with a colleague, a Finnish as a second language teacher, focused on artificial intelligence experiments in language teaching from

¹⁰ In Finnish: "Oppija keskiössä, työelämää palvelevat oppimiskokemukset"

CEFR A2 to B2 levels. To encourage discussion, we're planning to make the workshop conversational, so each of us will first deliver a short presentation as background. I'll be presenting the *AI Corner* module and some highlights from the two surveys I conducted.

What's more, at the time of writing this, I'm considering whether to submit a presentation abstract for the Language and Communication Teaching Days organized at Oulu University of Applied Sciences in October 2025 as well as the 2026 spring event of the Proflang Association of Languages for Professional Communication.

I might also offer to write a short column about the *AI Corner* project for the newsletter of the Confederation of Language Centres in Europe, CercleS. It's an organization that connects over 400 language centers, similar academic units, and other organizations (CercleS 2024). All LAB/LUT Language Centre teachers are members and can publish in the CercleS newsletter.

Finally, I've been invited to join a four-university project planning team. The current working title of the project is *AI Cosmos*¹¹. Among several other themes, we'll be planning the project around the use of AI tools to potentially help Finnish companies, other organizations, and employers better interact and communicate with international students, immigrants, and other employees from non-Finnish backgrounds. At the moment I'm writing this, the team is looking for funding for the project. While my *AI Corner* project doesn't align directly with the *AI Cosmos* project, I'm hoping to be able to apply and share some of the knowledge and expertise I've developed throughout the *AI Corner* project.

5.3 AI Corner Future Use and Updates

My initial idea was that *AI Corner* could be integrated into compulsory English language and communication courses offered at the Language Centre, but this would've likely required updating their learning outcomes and parts of their syllabi. While any English teacher teaching compulsory English courses at the Language Centre can still freely use *AI Corner* as a component in their course, my team manager and I discussed that it would be good to offer it as a standalone 1-ECTS on-demand elective online course outside of the compulsory courses. As a result, we have decided it'll be launched in autumn 2025 under a new name: *English and AI: Terminology, Ethics and Writing*.

¹¹ In Finnish: *Tekoälykosmos*.

To maximize learner access, participation and reach, we'll make the course available through multiple channels and platforms. It'll be offered to all enrolled LAB and LUT students, exchange students, and open university students. For optimal reach, it'll be available on the new Digivisio opin.fi platform and in the course catalog of the Cross-Institutional Study Information Service for Finnish higher education (see Opin.fi 2024; LAB.fi 2025).

While working to complete this report, I've begun working on course updates because of new tools. For instance, Poe.com has launched a new feature, Poe Apps, described as follows: "Poe Apps [...] make it easy to build visual interfaces on top of any combination of the existing models on Poe and custom logic expressed in Javascript." (Poe.com 2025). To create apps, the user simply needs to access the App-Creator tool, currently powered by Anthropic's Claude 3.7 Sonnet, and start prompting in natural language. I've begun testing the feature and created an interactive app for learners to review course topics (Image 15).

Image 15. English and AI app on Poe.com (screenshot)

I've also added a new assignment to the course Moodle page with a link to the Poe.com *English and AI* app. This is shown below in Image 16. Learners are instructed to sign in with their university credentials, go through the *English and AI* module, and submit a screenshot after completion. The app issues a simple completion certificate.

Assignment
English and AI on Poe.com

Make a submission

Hidden from students

- **English and AI (on Poe.com)**
 - Sign in and complete the *English and AI* module on the Poe.com platform. The module helps you review some of the course topics.
 - For access and better privacy, use your student credentials (e.g. @student.lab.fi, @student.lut.fi, or similar) rather than your personal email.
 - Submit a screenshot of the completed module = your *Certificate* (shown at the bottom part of the *Conclusion* section).
 - **Note:** This is experimental. Please contact the instructor in case of problems using the module on Poe.com.

Image 16. English and AI assignment

As I've briefly mentioned in Chapter 4.2, at the time of writing this report, I created and added a new assignment to *Module 3: AI Writing* called AI vs. Human Writing. This requires learners to take a short quiz on the GPTZero¹² website. The quiz is focused on identifying whether a specific text was written by a human, an AI, or possibly both. As shown in Image 17 below, the activity on the course page instructs learners to take the quiz on the GPTZero website and, upon completing it, upload a screenshot of their quiz results.

AI vs. Human Writing

To do: Make a submission

Take the quiz to see if you can identify whether a passage was written by AI, human, or both.

- **AI vs. Human: Can you tell?**

To complete this activity, take a screenshot of your test result and submit the screenshot here.

Image 17. AI vs. Human assignment

What's more, I'm planning to update the contents of *Module 3: AI Writing* by adding sample prompts to the materials and to create a fourth discussion activity in the *Activity* section, where learners will be instructed to do a small AI-scaffolded writing activity based on the basic writing process (prewriting, drafting, revising, and editing and proofreading).

Finally, due to the name change from *AI Corner* to *English and AI: Terminology, Ethics and Writing*, I'll need to update some texts and instructions on the course page and revise several course videos. To minimize this work, however, and to avoid updating everything (such as course graphics), I'll mention in the updated videos that the course is also known as *AI Corner*.

¹² GPTZero is an AI detection tool. Here is the link to the quiz: <https://gptzero.fillout.com/ai-quiz>

Reflection and Conclusion

In this report, I've documented the design and implementation of *AI Corner*, an introductory module on generative AI (GenAI) in English and intended to be used in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction. To reflect on the *AI Corner* project here, I've decided to apply the *AI Literacy and Integration Road Map* explained in Paiz, Toncelli and Kostka (2025). While they introduce the road map as a tool to determine one's journey ahead, I'm using it in Table 15 to look back and summarize my professional journey, while also listing future actions.

Table 15. AI Literacy and Integration Road Map: AI Corner (image: Paiz, Toncelli & Kostka 2025)

<p>LAYING THE FOUNDATION Starting your journey and learning about the fundamentals of critical AI literacy.</p> <p>1</p>	<p>1) Laying the foundation Became aware of AI's potential impact on education. ChatGPT launched. Participated in AI-focused training sessions and webinars to build foundational knowledge.</p>
<p>2</p> <p>EXPLORING MORE Expanding your understanding of AI tools and beginning to experiment with them in.</p>	<p>2) Exploring more Continued attending AI-focused training sessions and webinars to deepen expertise. Attended a webinar featuring Sidney Dobrin, the author of <i>AI and Writing</i> (2023). Experimented with various AI tools.</p>
<p>INNOVATING & PILOTING Starting to integrate AI tools to enhance teaching and seeking feedback to refine your implementation.</p> <p>3</p>	<p>3) Innovating and piloting Created a project plan and pitched the <i>AI Corner</i> idea. Administered a survey about students' use of and views on AI. Started creating <i>AI corner</i> materials and designing <i>AI Corner</i>. Piloted the module and administered an exit feedback survey.</p>
<p>4</p> <p>GUIDING & EMPOWERING Leading conversations where possible and exploring more systematic and sustained applications of AI tools.</p>	<p>4) Guiding and empowering Published an AI-literacy related blog post and an article about AI detectors on LAB's website. Presented survey results to colleagues at the Language Centre. Presented survey results to LAB teachers at a LAB DigiPeda Days workshop. Published survey results in an article in <i>Kielivirtaa Saimaalta</i>.</p>
<p>MOBILIZING A NETWORK Collaborating with peers in- and outside of your institution to exchange ideas and shape conversations about AI policy.</p> <p>5</p>	<p>5) Mobilizing a network Several colleagues acted as sparring partners for the project. Participated in the <i>DigiErko – Learning Design and Instruction</i> course. Became the Language Centre's representative in the LAB AI Expert Group. Project listed on the <i>Artificial Intelligence at LUT and LAB</i> intranet page.</p> <p>Future Will launch <i>AI Corner</i> as a standalone 1-ECTS online course, <i>English and AI: Terminology, Ethics and Writing</i>, offered through various platforms and channels. Will update the course and explore new tools and add new features and activities to the course (e.g., Poe Apps). Will present the project in internal webinars at LAB/LUT. Will present the project in various external events.</p>

I'd also like to revisit McKenney and Reeve's model for educational design research (Figure 22), which I've introduced in Chapter 2.1, and briefly explain how my road map, and therefore the whole *AI Corner* project process, aligns with the model.

Stages 1 and 2 of my road map align with the Analysis/Exploration phase of the model. This is where I surveyed students' use of AI tools through the *Students' Use of AI* questionnaire and deepened my expertise and understanding of AI tools and their impact on higher education pedagogy. Since McKenney and Reeve's model illustrates an iterative process, my future plans to update *AI Corner* and keep exploring new tools represent a new exploration phase.

Parts of stage 2 of the road map relate to the Design/Construction phase of the model. This is where I began creating materials and designing *AI Corner* on Moodle. My work was informed by AI Literacy and TPACK, as well as learning experience design and my participation in the *Digivisio – Learning Design and Instruction* course. Additionally, my plans to add new features and activities to *AI Corner* are part of the next iteration of the Design/Construction phase.

Parts of stage 3 of my road map correspond to the Evaluation/Reflection phase of the model. For instance, the exit feedback survey after piloting *AI Corner* corresponds with evaluation and reflection. Mapping my journey in this chapter is also part of reflection.

Finally, stages 4 and 5 of my road map represent the Implementation part of McKenney and Reeve's model. This, for instance, includes my dissemination efforts, and the Future section in my roadmap is intended to include ideas for maturing the intervention (i.e. *AI Corner*).

Figure 22. Generic model for educational design research (McKenney & Reeves 2018, 83)

Throughout the *AI Corner* project, I've gained valuable insights into GenAI and its impact on higher education pedagogy. While experimenting with numerous GenAI tools, I've learned how to prompt GenAIs, and more importantly, I've learned how certain of these tools can, when used effectively and responsibly, enrich my pedagogy. GenAIs can, equally well, be used for reflection and professional self-development. However, I've also become aware that using GenAI tools can sometimes become a slippery slope where users must be cautious and mindful to maintain their own voice and agency. As an educator, I'm responsible for ensuring that learners become familiar with using GenAI tools for professional purposes but also comprehend their potential risks.

While the process was smooth, overall, and I was fortunate to have both collegial and managerial support throughout the *AI Corner* project, I'd also like to briefly note here a minor challenge along the way. The English team had a team meeting to launch autumn semester 2024. A colleague of mine and I were acting as team coordinators and running the meeting. A recently hired new English instructor asked—rightly, of course—whether we had any AI policies in place, which then sprang up a more general conversation on AI. We mentioned the *English Team AI Policies* document I and two of my colleagues had created in spring 2024. I hadn't really introduced my project idea to the team, although most team members knew of my interest in how GenAI was developing and impacting our work. My team coordinator colleague, who knew about it, mentioned that I was working the *AI Corner* module, which could be used as component in compulsory English courses. Some team members began expressing somewhat strong opinions against whether it's really English language and communication instructors' task to teach the use of these tools. All this took me by surprise; GenAI was not on our meeting agenda, so I wasn't prepared to defend my position. I felt slightly taken aback and demotivated after the conversation but finalized the *AI Corner* module in early autumn 2024 and began feeling more motivated when collecting *AI Corner* exit feedback from the *AI Corner* pilot participants at the end of the semester.

To conclude, I'd like to review one key point I made in the introduction: that ESP teaching could offer a good home for instructing responsible GenAI use. While some ESP instructors are willing to take this suggestion with open arms, others—like some of my naysaying colleagues—will take this with a grain of salt. There's also, of course, the gray area in between, but I'd like to briefly address the naysayers and grain-of-salt instructors specifically.

While I'm not suggesting there's any need to jump aboard the current AI hype train or try to stay up to date on all possible developments AI—these seem to come if not daily, weekly—

let's emphasize here what could be called the pragmatic ESP approach. Since users typically interact with GenAI tools in natural language, either through writing or speech, and more importantly, since GenAI tools are often used specifically for communicative purposes—that is, as *assistive communication tools*—professional language and communication instruction in higher education offers a natural setting for learners to experiment with these tools and gain experience in their professional, responsible use. I'd like to argue that this aligns particularly well with ESP's needs-based approach, where the focus is commonly on helping learners acquire up-to-date English and communication skills needed for work or studies.

My *AI Corner* project represents one modest attempt at introducing GenAI in the context of English language and communication instruction, specifically in Finnish higher education. It's my humble wish that this work might inspire, perhaps even encourage, my fellow higher education ESP instructors—as well as anyone else interested in exploring GenAI's impact on pedagogy—to begin their own journey in creating and designing pedagogical interventions around GenAI to help their learners become better equipped for near-future workplaces.

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Appendix 1: Students' Use of AI 2024 (Spring)

All open-ended question items deleted from the public version of the report for privacy and available on request.

Total number of respondents: 91

1. My home university:

Number of respondents: 91

	n	Percent
LAB University of Applied Sciences	48	52,7%
LUT University	43	47,3%

2. My unit/faculty

Number of respondents: 48

	n	Percent
Business	44	91,7%
Technology	4	8,3%
Design	0	0,0%
Social and Health Care	0	0,0%

3. My faculty/school:

Number of respondents: 37

	n	Percent
Business School	13	35,1%
School of Engineering Science	19	51,4%
School of Energy Systems	5	13,5%

4. The course I am enrolled in:

Number of respondents: 48

	n	Percent
English for Work	10	20,8%
English for Professional Communication	21	43,8%
Writing for Digital Media	3	6,2%
Academic Writing	0	0,0%
Business Writing	2	4,2%
Other	12	25,0%

Answers given into textfield

Option names	Text
Other	Meetings and presentations
Other	Meetings and Presentations
Other	Meetings & Presentations
Other	Meetings and Presentations
Other	Meetings and presentations
Other	Meetings and Presentations
Other	meeting and presentations
Other	Meetings and presentation
Other	Meetings & Presentations
Other	Meetings and Presentations
Other	Meetings and Presentations

5. The course I am enrolled in:

Number of respondents: 42

	n	Percent
English for Professional Development	6	14,3%
Yhteiskunta- ja viestintätieteiden tekstitaidot	21	50,0%
Writing for Digital Media	2	4,7%
Academic Writing	4	9,5%
Business Writing	7	16,7%
Other	2	4,8%

Answers given into textfield

Option names	Text
Other	KE00CC64-3031
Other	English prep course

6. My average writing skill level in English:

Number of respondents: 91

	n	Percent
A1 Beginner	2	2,2%
A2 Pre-intermediate	1	1,1%
B1 Intermediate	14	15,4%
B2 Upper-intermediate	35	38,4%
C1 Advanced	24	26,4%
C2 Fully proficient	8	8,8%
Prefer not to answer/not sure	7	7,7%

7. I know the following AI tool(s):

Number of respondents: 91, selected answers: 297

	n	Percent
Open AI's ChatGPT 3.5 (generative AI, chatbot, free version)	78	85,7%
Open AI's ChatGPT 4 (generative AI, chatbot, paid version)	35	38,5%
Google's Bard/Gemini (generative AI, chatbot)	15	16,5%

Microsoft's Bing Chat/Copilot (generative AI, chatbot)	38	41,8%
Pi.ai (generative AI, chatbot)	0	0,0%
Grammarly (AI-powered writing assistant)	54	59,3%
Microsoft's Editor in MS Office (AI-powered writing assistant)	26	28,6%
Wordtune (AI-powered writing assistant)	1	1,1%
QuillBot (AI-powered writing assistant)	14	15,4%
ProWritingAid (AI-powered writing assistant)	3	3,3%
Dalle-E (AI-powered image generation tool)	10	11,0%
Adobe Firefly (AI-powered image generation tool)	4	4,4%
Midjourney (AI-powered image generation tool)	5	5,5%
Ideogram (AI-powered image generation tool)	1	1,1%
Stable Diffusion (AI-powered image generation tool)	1	1,1%
Imagine with Meta (AI-powered image generation tool)	2	2,2%
Synthesia (AI-powered video generation tool)	0	0,0%
HeyGen (AI-powered video generation tool)	0	0,0%
Speechify (AI-powered text-to-speech tool)	2	2,2%
LOVO.ai (AI-powered text to speech tool)	0	0,0%
Others (please specify)	4	4,4%
None of the above	4	4,4%

8. Use of AI tools for coursework and studying in English (=homework, assignments, thesis work...)

Number of respondents: 91

	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Average	Median
I have used AI tools for brainstorming coursework ideas in English.	3,3%	41,7%	26,4%	28,6%	2,8	3,0
I have used AI tools to better understand coursework instructions in English.	5,5%	22,0%	26,4%	46,1%	3,1	3,0
I have used AI tools to get general feedback on my coursework in English.	3,3%	18,7%	23,1%	54,9%	3,3	4,0
I have used AI tools to check my coursework for grammatical mistakes in English.	29,6%	26,4%	15,4%	28,6%	2,4	2,0
I have used AI tools to check my coursework for typos and spelling mistakes in English.	29,6%	28,6%	17,6%	24,2%	2,4	2,0

I have used AI tools to check my coursework for punctuation mistakes in English.	20,9%	24,2%	18,7%	36,2%	2,7	3,0
I have used AI tools to summarize source texts for my coursework in English.	0,0%	18,7%	24,2%	57,1%	3,4	4,0
I have used AI tools to better understand source text for my coursework in English.	4,4%	20,9%	26,4%	48,3%	3,2	3,0
I have used AI tools to edit the tone and style of my coursework in English.	1,1%	12,1%	31,9%	54,9%	3,4	4,0
I have used AI tools to generate complete paragraphs for my coursework in English.	1,1%	6,6%	18,7%	73,6%	3,6	4,0
I have used AI tools to generate complete essays or other long texts for my coursework in English.	0,0%	4,4%	9,9%	85,7%	3,8	4,0
I have used AI tools to translate text passages for my coursework in English.	2,2%	19,8%	23,1%	54,9%	3,3	4,0
I have used AI tools to generate presentation materials for my coursework in English.	0,0%	5,5%	24,2%	70,3%	3,6	4,0
I have used AI tools to generate images for my coursework in English.	0,0%	8,8%	11,0%	80,2%	3,7	4,0
I have used AI tools to generate videos for my coursework in English.	0,0%	2,2%	3,3%	94,5%	3,9	4,0
I have used AI tools to generate audio for my coursework in English.	0,0%	2,2%	2,2%	95,6%	3,9	4,0
Total	6,3%	16,4%	18,9%	58,4%	3,3	4,0

9. Your comments about using AI tools for coursework and studying in English:

10. Knowledge of basic AI concepts

Number of respondents: 91

	Yes	Partly	No	Average	Median
I know what generative AI means.	46,1%	42,9%	11,0%	1,6	2,0
I know what it means that generative AI tools may occasionally hallucinate.	36,2%	28,6%	35,2%	2,0	2,0
I know what it means that AI is sometimes anthropomorphized.	12,1%	27,5%	60,4%	2,5	3,0
I know what prompting means in the context of generative AI.	30,8%	26,4%	42,8%	2,1	2,0
I know what Large Language Model (LLM) means.	11,0%	27,5%	61,5%	2,5	3,0
I know what reinforcement learning means in the context of machine learning.	16,5%	36,3%	47,2%	2,3	2,0
I know what AI ethics means.	39,6%	41,7%	18,7%	1,8	2,0
I know what AI Literacy means.	24,2%	37,4%	38,4%	2,1	2,0
Total	27,1%	33,5%	39,4%	2,1	2,0

11. Knowledge of/opinions on AI policies

Number of respondents: 91

	Yes	Partly	No	Average	Median
I am familiar with data privacy issues in the context of generative AI.	42,9%	47,2%	9,9%	1,7	2,0
I am familiar with using AI tools responsibly to generate content.	52,7%	36,3%	11,0%	1,6	1,0
I have been instructed in detail on how to use AI tools by my teachers.	29,7%	39,5%	30,8%	2,0	2,0
I know how to cite the use of generative AI tools in coursework.	26,4%	41,7%	31,9%	2,1	2,0
I am familiar with my university's AI policies.	59,3%	34,1%	6,6%	1,5	1,0
I would accept it if teachers used AI tools to provide automated feedback on my coursework.	31,9%	41,7%	26,4%	1,9	2,0
I would accept it if teachers submitted my coursework to AI systems for fully-automated grading.	17,8%	33,3%	48,9%	2,3	2,0
Total	37,2%	39,1%	23,6%	1,9	2,0

12. Your comments about basic AI concepts and AI policy:

13. Opinions about AI tools and their use to communicate in English

Number of respondents: 91

	Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Average	Median
Knowing how to use AI tools is an important professional skill.	28,6%	42,8%	15,4%	13,2%	0,0%	2,1	2,0
Using AI tools to help with work is ethically acceptable.	12,1%	49,4%	26,4%	11,0%	1,1%	2,4	2,0
Becoming reliant on AI tools to help write in English is a risk.	34,0%	33,0%	28,6%	3,3%	1,1%	2,0	2,0
It is easy to evaluate whether AI-generated content in English is accurate.	5,5%	26,4%	46,1%	20,9%	1,1%	2,9	3,0
Using AI tools for help makes my writing appear less interesting in English.	4,4%	16,5%	46,1%	33,0%	0,0%	3,1	3,0
It is easy to evaluate whether AI-generated feedback on my writing in English is accurate.	2,2%	30,8%	51,6%	14,3%	1,1%	2,8	3,0

I know how to apply AI prompting techniques to get the kind of output I want in English.	7,7%	38,4%	38,5%	13,2%	2,2%	2,6	3,0
Using AI tools for help makes my writing smoother in English.	11,0%	45,0%	35,2%	7,7%	1,1%	2,4	2,0
It is easy to write excellent English without using AI tools for help.	8,8%	36,2%	28,6%	25,3%	1,1%	2,7	3,0
Using AI tools for help makes me a more confident writer in English.	13,2%	36,2%	28,6%	16,5%	5,5%	2,6	3,0
Using AI to help me write in English can reduce my stress.	6,6%	41,7%	27,5%	17,6%	6,6%	2,8	3,0
Using AI tools for help makes my writings in English grammatically better.	17,6%	45,0%	26,4%	7,7%	3,3%	2,3	2,0
Total	12,6%	36,8%	33,3%	15,3%	2,0%	2,6	3,0

14. Opinions about AI risks

Number of respondents: 91

	Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Average	Median
Copyright issues are a risk when using AI tools.	38,4%	38,5%	17,6%	5,5%	0,0%	1,9	2,0
Data privacy issues are a risk when using AI tools.	29,7%	48,3%	16,5%	5,5%	0,0%	2,0	2,0
Increased carbon dioxide emissions are a risk when using AI tools.	7,7%	13,2%	54,9%	13,2%	11,0%	3,1	3,0
Using outsourced workers in third world countries to train AI models is a risk when using AI tools.	15,4%	30,8%	49,4%	3,3%	1,1%	2,4	3,0
Total	22,8%	32,7%	34,6%	6,9%	3,0%	2,3	2,0

15. Your comments about AI tools and their use to communicate in English and AI risks

Appendix 2: AI Corner Pilot Exit Feedback 2024 (Autumn)

All open-ended question items deleted from the public version of the report for privacy and available on request.

Total number of respondents: 53

1. My home university:

Number of respondents: 53

	n	Percent
LAB University of Applied Sciences	47	88,7%
LUT University	6	11,3%

2. My unit/faculty

Number of respondents: 47

	n	Percent
Business	46	97,9%
Technology	1	2,1%
Design	0	0,0%
Social and Health Care	0	0,0%

3. My faculty/school:

Number of respondents: 6

	n	Percent
Business School	3	50,0%
School of Engineering Science	2	33,3%
School of Energy Systems	1	16,7%

4. My average skill level in English:

Number of respondents: 53

	n	Percent
Beginner (A1)	0	0,0%
Preintermediate (A2)	1	1,9%
Intermediate (B1)	7	13,2%
Upper-intermediate (B2)	19	35,9%
Advanced (C1)	19	35,8%
Fully proficient (C2)	5	9,4%

Prefer not to answer/not sure	2	3,8%
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5. I was familiar with the following AI tool(s) already before AI Corner:

Number of respondents: 53, selected answers: 209

	n	Percent
Open AI's ChatGPT (generative AI, chatbot)	50	94,3%
Google Gemini (generative AI, chatbot)	17	32,1%
Microsoft Copilot (generative AI, chatbot)	34	64,2%
Pi.ai (generative AI, chatbot)	0	0,0%

Grammarly (writing assistant)	40	75,5%
Microsoft Editor in MS Office (writing assistant)	18	34,0%
Wordtune (writing assistant)	1	1,9%
QuillBot (writing assistant)	19	35,8%
ProWritingAid (writing assistant)	2	3,8%
Dalle-E (image generation tool)	5	9,4%
Adobe Firefly (image generation tool)	4	7,5%
Midjourney (image generation tool)	7	13,2%
Ideogram (image generation tool)	3	5,7%
Stable Diffusion (image generation tool)	4	7,5%
Imagine with Meta (image generation tool)	2	3,8%
Synthesia (video generation tool)	1	1,9%
HeyGen (video generation tool)	0	0,0%
Others (please specify)	1	1,9%
None of the above	1	1,9%

Answers given into textfield

Option names	Text
Others (please specify)	Hesse write, Canva

6. I use AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT, Grammarly) on average X hours daily

Number of respondents: 47

Min value	Max value	Average	Median	Sum	Standard Deviation
0,0	3,0	0,9	0,5	41,5	0,8

7. Use of AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT, Grammarly) for coursework in English (e.g. homework, thesis work...)

Number of respondents: 53

	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Average	Median
I use AI tools for brainstorming coursework ideas in English.	20,7%	43,4%	18,9%	17,0%	2,3	2,0
I use AI tools to better understand coursework instructions in English.	18,9%	32,1%	24,5%	24,5%	2,5	2,0
I use AI tools to get general feedback on my coursework in English.	7,5%	41,5%	20,8%	30,2%	2,7	3,0
I use AI tools to check my coursework for grammatical mistakes in English.	37,7%	35,9%	15,1%	11,3%	2,0	2,0
I use AI tools to check my coursework for typos and spelling mistakes in English.	34,0%	37,7%	13,2%	15,1%	2,1	2,0

I use AI tools to check my coursework for punctuation mistakes in English.	20,7%	30,2%	20,8%	28,3%	2,6	2,0
I use AI tools to summarize source texts for my coursework in English.	13,2%	22,6%	34,0%	30,2%	2,8	3,0
I use AI tools to better understand source text for my coursework in English.	13,2%	39,6%	24,5%	22,7%	2,6	2,0
I use AI tools to edit the tone and style of my coursework in English.	15,1%	17,0%	26,4%	41,5%	2,9	3,0
I use AI tools to generate complete paragraphs for my coursework in English.	3,8%	17,0%	24,5%	54,7%	3,3	4,0
I use AI tools to generate complete essays or other long texts for my coursework in English.	5,7%	11,3%	17,0%	66,0%	3,4	4,0
I use AI tools to translate text passages for my coursework in English.	11,3%	15,1%	35,9%	37,7%	3,0	3,0
I use AI tools to generate presentation materials for my coursework in English.	5,7%	20,7%	13,2%	60,4%	3,3	4,0
I use AI tools to generate images for my coursework in English.	1,9%	22,6%	26,4%	49,1%	3,2	3,0
I use AI tools to generate videos for my coursework in English.	5,7%	5,7%	9,4%	79,2%	3,6	4,0
I use AI tools to generate audio for my coursework in English.	3,8%	3,8%	13,2%	79,2%	3,7	4,0
Total	13,7%	24,8%	21,1%	40,4%	2,9	3,0

8. AI Corner: The learning outcomes are clear.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES
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12. AI Corner: I have learned for what purposes AI tools might be useful.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	1	1	2	11	38	53	46	49
Percent	1,9 %	1,9 %	3,8 %	20,8 %	71,7 %	100,0 %	4,6	92,5 %									

13. Please elaborate/your notes:

14. AI Corner: I have learned about some of the risks of using AI tools.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	0	0	4	13	36	53	4,6	49
Percent	0,0 %	0,0 %	7,5 %	24,5 %	67,9 %	100,0 %	4,6	92,5 %									

15. Please elaborate/your notes:

16. AI Corner: I have learned some basics of using AI tools for studying.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	2	2	4	10	35	53	44	45
Percent	3,8 %	3,8 %	7,5 %	18,9 %	66,0 %	100,0 %	4,4	85,0 %									

17. Please elaborate/your notes:

18. AI Corner: I have learned some basics of using AI tools for writing in English.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	2	2	4	15	30	53	4,3	45
Percent	3,8 %	3,8 %	7,5 %	28,3 %	56,6 %	100,0 %	4,3	85,0 %									

19. Please elaborate/your notes:

20. AI Corner: I have learned some basics of using AI tools for image generation.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	1	3	7	14	28	53	4,2	4,2
Percent	1,9 %	5,7 %	13,2 %	26,4 %	52,8 %	100,0 %	4,2	79,3 %									

21. Please elaborate/your notes:

22. AI Corner: I have learned some basics of prompting AI for better output in English.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	2	1	4	17	29	53	4,3	46
Percent	3,8 %	1,9 %	7,5 %	32,1 %	54,7 %	100,0 %	4,3	86,8 %									

23. Please elaborate/your notes:

24. AI Corner: The workload is about ... ECTS credits.

Number of respondents: 53

Min value	Max value	Average	Median	Sum	Standard Deviation
1,0	2,0	1,8	2,0	94,8	0,4

25. Please elaborate/your notes:

26. AI Corner: The page is easy to navigate.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	0	0	3	7	43	53	48	50
Percent	0,0 %	0,0 %	5,7 %	13,2 %	81,1 %	100,0 %	4,8	94,4 %									

27. Please elaborate/your notes:

28. AI Corner: The page is visually clear.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	0	0	3	7	4	5	4,	5
														3	3	8	0
Percent	0,0 %	0,0 %	5,7 %	13,2 %	81,1 %	100,0 %	4,8	94,4 %									

29. Please elaborate/your notes:

30. AI Corner: The instructions (e.g. for modules, quizzes, activities) are clear.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	0	0	2	9	4	5	4	5
Percent	0,0 %	0,0 %	3,8 %	17,0 %	79,2 %	100,0 %	4,8	96,3 %									

31. Please elaborate/your notes:

32. AI Corner: The materials are interesting.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES										
									N	1	1	2	13	36	53	45	49	
Percent	1,9 %	1,9 %	3,8 %	24,5 %	67,9 %	100,0 %	4,5	92,5 %										

33. Please elaborate/your notes:

34. AI Corner: The materials are up-to-date.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES									
									N	0	1	4	5	4	5	4,	4
Percent	0,0 %	1,9 %	7,5 %	9,4 %	81,1 %	100,0 %	4,7	90,6 %									

35. Please elaborate/your notes:

36. AI Corner: The activities are interesting.

Number of respondents: 53

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES										
									N	0	1	4	13	35	53	45	48	
Percent	0,0 %	1,9 %	7,5 %	24,5 %	66,0 %	100,0 %	4,5	90,6 %										

37. Please elaborate/your notes:

41. AI Corner: I found the AICorner chatbot useful 😊.

Number of respondents: 19

	Very Difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very Easy	Total	Mean	CES											
									N	1	3	5	6	4	19	35	10		
Percent	5,3 %	15,8 %	26,3 %	31,6 %	21,1 %	100,0 %	3,5	52,7 %											

42. Please elaborate/your notes:

43. Did you have any technical problems using the AI Corner page?

44. Did you notice any errors in the AI Corner materials?

45. What additional topics/ features would you like to see included in AI Corner?

46. After taking AI Corner...

Number of respondents: 53

	Yes	Partly	No	Average	Median
I know what generative AI means.	92,5%	7,5%	0,0%	1,1	1,0
I know what it means that generative AIs may sometimes hallucinate.	83,0%	13,2%	3,8%	1,2	1,0
I know what it means that AI is sometimes anthropomorphized.	66,0%	32,1%	1,9%	1,4	1,0
I know what prompting means in the context of generative AI.	92,5%	7,5%	0,0%	1,1	1,0
I know what Large Language Model (LLM) means.	71,7%	24,5%	3,8%	1,3	1,0
I know what AI ethics means.	94,3%	5,7%	0,0%	1,1	1,0
I know what weak AI means.	81,1%	17,0%	1,9%	1,2	1,0
I know what strong AI means.	81,1%	17,0%	1,9%	1,2	1,0
Total	82,8%	15,6%	1,7%	1,2	1,0

47. After taking AI Corner...

Number of respondents: 53

	Yes	Partly	No	Average	Median
I am familiar with data privacy issues in the context of generative AI.	92,5%	7,5%	0,0%	1,1	1,0
I am familiar with using AI tools responsibly to generate content.	90,6%	9,4%	0,0%	1,1	1,0
I am familiar with my university's AI policies.	90,6%	9,4%	0,0%	1,1	1,0
I am familiar with using AI tools for writing in English.	92,5%	7,5%	0,0%	1,1	1,0
Total	91,6%	8,5%	0,0%	1,1	1,0

48. My overall impression of AI Corner is...

Number of respondents: 52

Min value	Max value	Average	Median	Sum	Standard Deviation
3,0	5,0	4,6	5,0	239,0	0,6